

Complete lignocellulose conversion with integrated catalyst recycling yielding valuable aromatics and fuels

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Supplementary Figure 2 Representative GC-MS traces used to establish the identity of lignin depolymerization products using authentic standards. a) 4-Ethylguaiaicol (**3G**). b) 4-Propylguaiaicol (**2G**). c) 4-Ethylsyringol (**3S**). d) 4-Propylsyringol (**2S**). e) Dihydroconiferyl alcohol (**1G**). f) Dihydrosinapic alcohol (**1S**).

Supplementary Figure 3 Product formation profiles in reactions using pine lignocellulose. Reaction conditions: Cu2O-PMO (0.2 g), pine lignocellulose 1 g, methanol (10 mL), 3,5-dimethylphenol (20 mg), 180 °C, H₂ (40 bar).

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Supplementary Figure 15 ^1H - ^{13}C -HSQC (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$) of pine organosolv lignin, full spectrum shown.

Supplementary Figure 16 ^1H - ^{13}C -HSQC (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of a control reaction carried out without catalyst under N_2 (Control 1), full spectrum shown.

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Supplementary Figure 28 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **1G** isolated from reaction using pine lignocellulose.

Supplementary Figure 29 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound **1S** isolated from reaction using maple lignocellulose.

Supplementary Figure 30 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound **1S** isolated from reaction using maple lignocellulose.

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Supplementary Figure 32 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **3G**.

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Supplementary Figure 34 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 4.

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Supplementary Figure 39 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 6Cy.

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Supplementary Figure 41 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 7.

Supplementary Figure 42 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 7.

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Supplementary Figure 44 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) spectrum of compound **7S**.

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Supplementary Figure 46 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 8.

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Supplementary Figure 49 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 9b.

Supplementary Figure 50 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 9b.

Supplementary Figure 51 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **9c**.

Supplementary Figure 52 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **9c**.

Supplementary Figure 53 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 9d.

Supplementary Figure 54 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 9d.

Supplementary Figure 55 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 9e.

Supplementary Figure 56 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 9e.

Supplementary Figure 57 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 10.

Supplementary Figure 58 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 10.

Supplementary Figure 59 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 11.

Supplementary Figure 60 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 11.

Supplementary Figure 61 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 12a.

Supplementary Figure 62 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 12a.

Supplementary Figure 63 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **12b**.

Supplementary Figure 64 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **12b**.

Supplementary Figure 65 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 12c.

Supplementary Figure 66 ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of compound 12c.

Supplementary Figure 67 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 13.

Supplementary Figure 68 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 13.

Supplementary Figure 69 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **14**.

Supplementary Figure 70 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **14**.

Supplementary Figure 71 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 15.

Supplementary Figure 72 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 15.

Supplementary Figure 73 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 3S.

Supplementary Figure 74 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 3S.

Supplementary Figure 75 ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 8S.

Supplementary Figure 76 ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound 8S.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1 Mild depolymerization (Step 1) of pine lignocellulose at different reaction conditions.

Entry	Substrate (mg)	Time(h)	Temperature (°C)	Methanol-solubles (mg) ^b	Methanol-insolubles (mg) ^c	Mass Balance (%)	Monomers (mg) ^d				Monomer Yield (%) ^e
							1G	2G	3G	Sum	
1 ^a	1000	18	180	70	790	86	25	3	1	29	10
2	1000	18	140	10	880	89	4	0	0	4	1
3	1000	18	220	140	680	82	22	12	2	36	13
4	1000	6	180	40	830	87	16	2	0	18	6
5	1000	2	180	30	870	90	14	1	0	15	5
6	1000	4	180	40	870	91	15	2	0	17	6
7	1000	12	180	70	800	87	22	2	1	25	9
8	1000	24	180	90	780	87	25	3	1	29	10
9	1000	36	180	90	770	86	25	3	1	29	10
10 ^f	2000	18	180	140	1800	97	44(40) ^g	4	0	48	9
11 ^h	10000	18	180	930	8730	97	239(220) ^g	25	12	276	10
12 ⁱ	200	18	180	80	100	90	5	2	1	8	4
13	500	18	180	40	370	82	9	1	0	10	6

Reaction conditions: Cu20-PMO 200 mg, methanol 10 mL, 180 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 18 h, 3,5-dimethylphenol 20 mg as an internal standard. a. Average yields of repeated 3 reactions are given. b. Weight of methanol soluble products excludes the weight of internal standard. c. Weight of methanol insoluble solid residue excludes the weight of the catalysts. d. Determined based on GC-FID measurement using calibration curves and internal standard. e. Monomer yield = $\text{weight}_{\text{monomers}} / \text{weight}_{\text{lignin}}$ [weight of lignin determined as shown in Supplementary Methods Section 7 and Supplementary Table 5] f. 400 mg Cu20-PMO was used. g. Weight of isolated pure product. h. Cu20-PMO 1 g, methanol 100 mL. i. Organosolv lignin extracted from pine lignocellulose was used as substrate.

1G: Dihydroconiferyl alcohol, **2G:** 4-Propylguaiacol, **3G:** 4-Ethylguaiacol.

Supplementary Table 2 Mild depolymerization reactions of lignocelluloses from different sources.

Entry	Substrate	Methanol-Solubles(mg) ^a	Methanol-Insolubles(mg) ^b	Mass Balance (%)	Monomers (mg) ^c							Monomer Yield (%) ^d
					1G	1S	2G	2S	3G	3S	Sum	
1	Pine	70	790	86	25	0	3	0	1	0	29	10
2	Walnut	140	810	95	13	15	5	13	0	2	48	9
3	Poplar	120	730	85	19	28	4	14	1	1	67	36
4	Oak	140	800	94	8	9	7	27	0	0	51	17
5	Beech	120	800	92	12	35	2	9	0	1	59	31
6	Maple	130	800	93	23(22) ^e	41(31) ^e	3	10	1	1	79	30
7	Alder	100	840	86	17	17	3	6	1	1	45	20
8	Cedar	120	800	92	24	0	8	0	4	0	36	10

Reaction conditions: Lignocellulose 1 g, Cu2O-PMO 200 mg, methanol 10 mL, 180 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 18 h, 3,5-dimethylphenol 20 mg as an internal standard. a. Weight of methanol soluble products excludes internal standard. b. Weight of methanol insoluble part excludes catalysts. c. Determined based on GC-FID measurement using calibration curves and internal standard. d. Monomer yield = weight_{monomers} / weight_{lignin}. [weight of lignin was determined as shown in Supplementary Methods Section 7 and Supplementary Table 5]. e. Isolated yield of pure product in mg, from a separate run under identical conditions.

1G: Dihydroconiferyl alcohol, **1S:** Dihydrosinapic alcohol, **2G:** 4-Propylguaiacol, **2S:** 4-Propylsyringol, **3G:** 4-Ethylguaiacol, **3S:** 4-Ethylsyringol.

Supplementary Table 3 Extraction of organosolv lignin from various lignocellulose sources including fractionation.^a

Lignocellulose	Methanol Solubles(g)	DCM Solubles(g)	DCM Insolubles(g)	Methanol-Insolubles(g)	Mass Balance ^b
Pine	0.13	0.105	0.026	0.79	92%
Walnut	0.22	0.150	0.069	0.69	91%
Poplar	0.19	0.112	0.077	0.72	91%
Oak	0.18	0.121	0.063	0.78	96%
Beech	0.22	0.160	0.044	0.73	95%
Maple	0.20	0.123	0.072	0.75	95%
Alder	0.16	0.131	0.068	0.73	89%
Cedar	0.21	0.155	0.065	0.76	97%

a. Conditions: Lignocellulose 1.0 g, methanol 10 mL, 18 h, 180 °C, N₂ 40 bar. b. Mass balance = (W_{methanol-soluble} + W_{methanol-insoluble}) / W_{lignocellulose}. Fractionation was carried out as described in Supplementary Methods Section 9.

Supplementary Table 4 Structure of organosolv lignins obtained from various sources displaying the corresponding syringyl/guaiacyl ratios and correlations with the S/G ratios of the monomeric products obtained upon depolymerization.

Lignocellulose	Lignin composition (%) ^a			S:G	
	S	G	H	Crude lignin	Lignin monomers ^b
Pine	0	100	0	0.0	0.0
Walnut	65	27	8	2.4	1.7
Poplar	57	43	0	1.3	1.8
Oak	71	29	0	2.5	2.4
Beech	73	27	0	2.8	3.0
Maple	65	35	0	1.9	1.9
Alder	61	39	0	1.5	1.1
Cedar	0	100	0	0.0	0.0

a. Determined by ¹H-¹³C-HSQC (peak area integrations of the corresponding signals). DCM soluble fractions were used for the analysis. Fractionation described in Supplementary Fig. 81. The corresponding NMR spectra are shown in Supplementary Figs. 19-26. b. Calculated based on the data shown in Supplementary Table 2.

Supplementary Table 5 Lignin content in lignocelluloses from various sources and the distribution of interunit linkages in the corresponding organosolv lignin.

Lignocellulose	Lignin Content (%) ^a	Distribution of inter-linkages (per 100 C9 units) ^b		
		β-O-4	β-β	β-5
Pine	28.6	8	3	7
Walnut	50.8	15	10	4
Poplar	18.6	9	7	3
Oak	30.2	9	12	5
Beech	18.8	17	10	4
Maple	26.0	13	11	5
Alder	23.0	18	10	5
Cedar	35.1	6	3	6

a. Determined by the ABSL method. b. Determined by ¹H-¹³C-HSQC analysis of the DCM soluble fraction of organosolv lignin. Fractionation described in Supplementary Fig. 81. The corresponding NMR spectra are shown in Supplementary Figs. 19-26.

Supplementary Table 6 Complete overview of GC-MS-FID signals, identification, quantification and designation obtained from the depolymerization of solid residue from pine lignocellulose (see Supplementary Fig. 5 for corresponding GC trace).

Peak	Retention time (minutes) ^a	Area ^b	Retention time (minutes) ^c	Identification ^d	Quality match %	Group ^e
1	3.605	168856096	3.62	Methanol	99	
2	3.823	1048253	3.84	Ethanol	91	A
3	4.095	213878	4.11	Isopropanol	72	A
4	5.13	1271908	5.14	1-Propanol	91	A
5	5.349	243877	5.37	Tetrahydrofuran	87	ET
6	5.818	730565	5.83	2-Butanol	83	A
7	6.918	5033283	6.92	2-methyl-1-Propanol	94	A
8	7.091	1095491	7.1	2-methoxy-Ethanol	91	HE
9	7.781	155270	7.75	Not identified	-	OT
10	8.175	653264	8.19	1-Butanol	95	A
11	8.263	114645	8.28	2-Pentanol	83	A
12	8.985	222308	9	3-Pentanol	90	A
13	9.097	272160	9.11	3-methyl-2-Butanol	83	A
14	9.423	698397	9.43	2-hydroxy-Butanoic acid ethyl ester	74	ES
15	10.261	177954	10.28	3-methoxy-2-Butanol	83	HE
16	11.428	2830300	11.44	2-methyl-1-Butanol	94	A
17	11.995	75086	12.01	1-methoxy-2-Butanol	90	A
18	12.09	54360	12.11	2-methyl-3-Pentanol	78	A
19	12.846	473976	12.86	1-Pentanol	90	A
20	13.217	56398	13.23	Pentanoic acid methyl ester	83	ES
21	13.459	144060	13.47	3-Hexanol	90	A
22	13.755	133360	13.77	Cyclopentanol	90	A
23	13.888	185601	13.91	2-Hexanol	83	A
24	14.451	113443	14.46	1,2-Ethandiol	50	A
25	14.562	265973	14.57	3-methoxy-Pentane	47	ET
26	15.785	262883	15.8	2-methoxy-Propane	47	ET
27	16.174	1164435	16.18	2-methyl-1-Pentanol	72	A
28	16.429	536348	16.44	2-methyl-Cyclopentanol	97	A
29	16.511	202606	16.52	2-ethyl-1-Butanol	78	A
30	16.677	94051	16.7	3-methyl-Cyclopentanol	53	A
31	16.865	1182621	16.87	2-methyl-Cyclopentanol	94	A
32	17.604	187093	17.62	2,3-Butanediol	83	A
33	17.899	126252	17.92	2,5-dimethyl-Cyclopentanone	81	A
34	18.093	281993	18.11	Tetrahydro-5,6-dimethyl-2H-pyran-2-one	53	ES
35	18.182	132732	18.19	2,3-Butanediol	83	A
36	18.529	164460	18.54	Butanoic acid methyl ester	35	ES
37	18.689	69986	18.7	Not identified	-	OT
38	18.889	412322	18.9	not identified	47	OT
39	19.015	153720	19.02	Cyclohexanol	90	A
40	19.09	95906	19.1	2,4-Dimethylcyclopentanol	43	A
41	19.243	73904	19.26	2,4-Dimethylcyclopentanol	43	A
42	19.506	648487	19.52	1-Methoxycyclohexane	50	ET
43	19.774	636079	19.78	(Tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)methanol,	83	A
44	19.97	618794	19.98	1-methyl-Cyclohexanol	72	A
45	20.192	225605	20.2	4-methoxy-1-Butanol	90	HE
46	20.369	453650	20.38	Cyclopentanemethanol	80	A
47	20.537	58379	20.55	2,3-dimethyl-1-Pentanol	43	A
48	20.764	148871	20.78	4-methoxy-Butanoic acid methyl ester	83	ES
49	21.276	620281	21.29	1-methyl-Cyclohexanol	72	A
50	21.448	291995	21.46	5,7-dimethyl-Undecane	43	OT
51	21.781	99175	21.79	1,3-dimethoxy-Cycloheptane	38	ET
52	21.907	106316	21.93	2,4-dimethyl-Heptane	30	OT
53	22.199	270384	22.22	3-ethyl-2,2-dimethyl-Oxirane	45	ET
54	22.287	98586	22.3	(5-Methyltetrahydrofuran-2-yl)methanol	47	AL
55	22.513	184068	22.53	Carbamic acid methyl ester	53	ES
56	22.661	65504	22.68	(1-methylpropyl)-Hydrazine	37	OT
57	22.78	165255	22.79	4-Hydroxy-3-hexanone	38	A
58	22.86	58182	22.87	Not identified	-	OT

59	23.033	205960	23.04	(Tetrahydro-2H-pyran-2-yl)methanol	78	A
60	23.201	76420	23.22	Not identified	-	OT
61	23.313	51808	23.33	Not identified	-	OT
62	23.467	55732	23.45	Not identified	-	OT
63	23.564	58786	23.58	Not identified	-	OT
64	24.079	163965	24.09	3-methyl-2-Butenol	30	A
65	24.476	64969	24.49	2-Buten-1-ol	72	A
66	24.554	134677	24.57	Ethoxyethene	43	ET
67	24.759	130495	24.78	Not identified	-	OT
68	25.173	60420	25.18	2-methyl-2-Propen-1-ol	72	A
69	25.523	109923	25.54	5-Methyl-1-heptanol	38	A
70	26.036	50365	26.05	Not identified	-	OT
71	26.149	68229	26.16	Not identified	-	OT
72	26.248	202556	26.26	1,5-dimethoxy-Pentane	83	ET
73	26.425	100530	26.44	Not identified	-	OT
74	26.558	123690	26.57	5-methoxy-Pentanoic acid methyl ester	83	ES
75	26.835	60875	26.85	Not identified	-	OT
76	28.232	90244	28.24	Not identified	-	OT
77	28.35	71290	28.37	Cyclic aliphatic	32	OT
78	28.493	63544	28.51	3,5-dimethyl-Cyclopentanol	37	AL
79	29.08	117374	29.09	Not identified	-	OT
80	31.86	56391	31.88	Not identified	-	OT
81	32.115	70443	32.13	Not identified	-	OT
82	32.352	74450	32.36	6-Nonen-1-ol	37	A
83	32.498	130359	32.51	1,5-Pentanediol	64	A
84	32.96	154418	32.97	Long chain aliphatic compound	35	OT
85	33.061	104368	33.07	1-ethyl-Cyclohexene	47	OT
86	33.415	56193	33.44	Not identified	-	OT
87	33.678	78166	33.69	Not identified	-	OT
88	33.86	63416	33.87	Not identified	-	OT
89	34.147	77703	34.16	1-methyl-4-(1-methylethyl)-Cyclohexene	53	OT
90	34.815	76344	34.85	Not identified	-	OT
91	35.293	96596	35.3	Not identified	-	OT
92	36.417	58436	36.44	Not identified	-	OT
93	36.775	86131	36.79	2,3-Dimethoxytoluene	74	ET
94	36.931	126512	36.95	1,6-Hexanediol	59	A
95	37.191	58247	37.21	Not identified	-	OT
96	37.967	65532	37.81	Not identified	-	OT
97	39.439	76869	39.45	Not identified	-	OT
98	40.121	68957	40.13	4-ethyl-2-methyl-Phenol	59	PH
99	40.33	72322	40.34	Not identified	-	OT
100	41.665	53777	41.67	Not identified	-	OT
101	41.984	68965	42	4-hydroxy-Benzeneacetic acid methyl ester	43	ES
102	43.62	75357	43.63	2-Methyl-4-propylphenol	90	PH
103	43.749	158210	43.76	2-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde	72	PH
104	45.311	51299	45.33	2',4'-Dihydroxy-3'-methylpropiophenone	56	PH
105	47.77	51420	47.78	Not identified	-	OT

a. retention time of peaks in GC-FID. b. Peak area of the GC-FID signal. c. retention time of peaks in GC-MS. d. Red: identified by spiking with authentic standard, Blue: similarity match above 90%. e. Compound assignment to groups: **A**: alcohol; **HE**: hydroxyl ether; **ET**: ether; **ES**: ester; **PH**: phenolic; **OT**: others.

Supplementary Table 7 Composition and quantification of the products obtained upon conversion of the solid residues from different lignocellulose sources.

Lignocellulose	Conversion (%) ^a	Selectivity (%) ^b										
		A	A'	HE	HE'	ET	ET'	ES	ES'	PH	PH'	OT
Pine	100	65.7	1.9	4.9	0	0.8	5.5	3.0	2.5	0.8	0.4	14.5
Walnut	92	52.4	8.9	7.7	0	2.1	1.8	8.3	1.6	0.5	0.4	16.3
Poplar	100	38.6	22.1	4.5	0	1.6	3.7	9.7	3.5	0.2	0.4	15.7
Oak	96	45.1	8.1	7.8	1.9	1.5	6.2	5.5	7.5	0	0	16.4
Beech	100	55.8	5.3	6.1	0.1	0.7	1.3	4.3	0.8	0	0	25.6
Maple	100	52.9	3.6	5.6	0.4	1.2	1.2	4.6	0.7	0	0	29.8
Alder	100	56.1	3.9	5.9	1.2	1.5	1.8	3.0	0.8	0	0	25.8
Cedar	97	44.2	8.1	11.8	1.7	0.9	1.3	4.0	2.7	0.2	0.7	24.4

a. conversion calculated based on the weight of the remaining solid residue. b. selectivity calculated based on GC-FID analysis; Explanation of groups: A: alcohols with high quality match ($\geq 70\%$); A': alcohols with low quality match (30%-70%); HE: hydroxyl ethers with high quality match ($\geq 70\%$); HE': hydroxyl ethers with low quality match (30%-70%); ET: ethers with high quality match ($\geq 70\%$); ET': ethers with low quality match (30%-70%); ES: esters with high quality match ($\geq 70\%$); ES': esters with low quality match (30%-70%); PH: phenolics with high quality match ($\geq 70\%$); PH': phenolics with low quality match (30%-70%); OT: others.

Supplementary Table 8 Nickel-catalyzed cross-coupling reaction of **8** with different amines.

Entry	Amines	Conversion %	GC Selectivity %			
			9	3G	10	Not identified
1		100	0	12	0	88
2		93	0	31	0	69
3		99	3	0	50	47
4		97	0	0	0	100
5		96	0	0	0	100
6		34	0	0	0	100
7		92	44	7	0	49
8		62	62	0	0	38
9		85	0	0	0	100
10		86	0	0	0	100
11		53	0	4	0	96
12		100	0	29	0	71
13		85	0	0	0	100
14		0	0	0	0	100
15		70	0	7	0	93
16		100	70	0	0	30
17		100	28	0	0	72
17 ^a		66	36	0	0	64
18		41	1	7	0	92
19		22	0	5	0	95
20		66	0	7	0	93

21		61	0	11	0	89
22		44	29	0	0	71
23		16	8	0	0	92
24		31	12	0	0	88
25		69	16	9	0	75
22^b		28	5	15	0	80
25^b		61	8	28	0	64

Reaction conditions: **8** 0.25 mmol, amines 0.35 mmol, Ni(COD)₂ 0.04 mmol, IPrHCl 0.08 mmol, amines 0.35 mmol, t-BuONa 0.5 mmol, toluene 2 mL, 80 °C, 21 h.

a. **8** 0.5 mmol was used. b. 100 °C.

Supplementary Notes

Supplementary Note 1 Characterization and properties of catalysts

The compositions of all PMO catalysts were determined by ICP analysis. A very good agreement with the theoretically expected values was found, indicating sufficient incorporation of the metal ions into the parent hydrotalcite structures.

Supplementary Table 9 Elemental composition of PMO catalysts.

Catalyst	Al (wt.%)	Cu (wt.%)	Mg (wt.%)	Ni (wt.%)
Mg/Al-PMO	12.4	-	32.6	-
Cu20-PMO	11.3	15.4	24.0	-
CuNi-PMO	12.4	11.7	24.3	5.3

The specific surface area of all catalysts was determined by BET measurements. All catalysts have similar surface area of around 200 m²/g. The addition of Cu slightly decreased the BET to 197.7 m²/g while the simultaneous presence of nickel and copper (188.5 m²/g) further decreased the surface area. The pore size also decreased for CuNi-PMO (13.5 nm) compared to the PMO catalyst (21.9 nm).

Supplementary Table 10 Composition and textural properties of the prepared PMO catalysts.

Catalyst	Theoretical composition ^a	Experimental composition ^b	Surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Average pore size (nm)
Mg/Al-PMO	Mg _{3.0} Al _{1.0}	Mg _{3.0} Al _{1.0}	233.8	0.91	21.9
Cu20-PMO	Cu _{0.6} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Cu _{0.6} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	197.7	0.96	21.2
CuNi-PMO	Cu _{0.4} Ni _{0.2} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Cu _{0.4} Ni _{0.2} Mg _{2.3} Al _{1.0}	188.5	0.91	13.5

a. Based on quantities of metal ions used during co-precipitation. b. Determined by ICP analysis.

Supplementary Figure 77 XRD patterns of the synthesized hydrotalcites (left) and the corresponding porous metal oxides (PMOs) after calcination (right).

The formation of the double-layered structure during HTC synthesis was confirmed by powder XRD measurements (Supplementary Fig. 77, left). These exhibited sharp diffraction peaks at 11.4°, 23.21°, 34.73° and broad reflections at 39.20°, 46.50°, 52.44°, 60.61° and 61.81° ascribed to the <003>, <006>, <012>, <015>, <018>, <110> and <113> planes referred to the trigonal hydrotalcite [JCPDS, 350965] according to reported data. The synthetic HTC were subsequently calcined at 460 °C overnight, during which the lamellar hydrotalcite structure was converted into an amorphous mixed-oxide composition, where three dominant peaks with the angle centered at 37°, 42° and 62.3° were ascribed to periclase (MgO, JCPDS, 431022) whereas no CuO (peaks at 23°, 28° and 31°) nor NiO oxide phase (peaks at 38°, 44° and 64°) could be detected (Supplementary Fig. 77, right), indicating a homogeneous dispersion of both active metals.

Supplementary Figure 78 TEM images of (a) fresh Cu₂₀-PMO catalysts, (b) Cu₂₀-PMO catalyst after one mild (180°C) and one supercritical (320°C) run, (c) elemental mapping of Cu₂₀-PMO catalyst after one mild (180°C) and one supercritical (320°C) run, (d) Cu₂₀-PMO catalyst after five mild (180°C) and five supercritical (320°C) runs, (e) elemental mapping of Cu₂₀-PMO catalyst after five mild (180°C) and five supercritical (320°C) runs.

TEM measurements of the fresh catalyst showed porous structures that did not display any agglomeration of the copper dopant, according to a homogeneous dispersion of the transition metals into the catalyst structure. The spent catalyst after the reaction in supercritical methanol was also imaged and a large number of dense nanoparticles with the range from 20 to 50 nm were detected,

attached to the surface of the sheets. According to the elemental mapping, the nanoparticles mainly contain Cu. The catalyst after the 5th double cycles (10 runs) shows aggregation of Mg and moderate aggregation of Cu, the likely reason for loss of activity.

Supplementary Note 2 Mechanistic studies regarding the cleavage of lignin β -O-4 model compounds

Supplementary Figure 79 Product formation profiles in reactions using the β -O-4 model compound **S1**. Reaction conditions: Cu20-PMO (0.1 g), **S1** (0.5 mmol), methanol (10 mL), 3,5-dimethylphenol (20 mg), 180 °C, H₂ (40 bar). (Full conversion of **S1** was observed within 1h)

Supplementary Figure 80 Product formation profiles in reactions using the β -O-4 model compound **S2**. Reaction conditions: Cu20-PMO (0.1 g), **S2** (0.5 mmol), methanol (10 mL), 3,5-dimethylphenol (20 mg), 180 °C, H₂ (40 bar).

In order to study the reactivity of the lignin β -O-4 linkage, we have studied the reactivity of simple β -O-4 model compounds. First, compound **S1** was reacted under reaction conditions that correspond to the ones used in the actual lignin depolymerization experiments. Product formation profiles were recorded by running a number of separate experiments for various reaction times (Supplementary Fig. 79). These revealed a very efficient cleavage of the β -O-4 linkage, to yield guaiacol (**b**) as expected, whereby the acetophenone (**a**) underwent rapid hydrogenation to 1-phenylethanol (**c**) under the reaction conditions. Further conversion of 1-phenylethanol (**c**) to ethylbenzene (**d**) likely via dehydration/hydrogenation or direct hydrogenolysis was also observed. Rapid hydrogenation of **S1** to the corresponding alcohol **S2** was also observed as expected under these reaction conditions. Thus, to clarify the reactivity of **S2** in this system, product formation profiles were recorded when **S2** was directly used as substrate (Supplementary Fig. 80), which yielded the same products as compound **S1**, guaiacol (**a**) and 1-phenylethanol (**c**), and ethylbenzene (**d**). In order to prove that a hydrogen neutral cleavage of the β -O-4 linkage via dehydrogenation/hydrogenation, a sequence of reaction steps also reported in the literature⁴, **S2** was treated over Cu20-PMO under N₂ atmosphere. Indeed, the formation of acetophenone (**a**) and guaiacol (**b**) was observed as expected (scheme below).

Based on these results we proposed the following reaction pathways involving in the cleavage of simple lignin model compounds **S1** and **S2**.

Based on this reactivity pattern, in the lignin reactions, the formation of model compound **S3** (β -Hydroxypropiovanillone) or/and the corresponding alcohol would be liberated upon the cleavage of the lignin β -O-4 linkage. Thus, we have also investigated the reactivity of **S3** under the reaction conditions to prove the feasibility of the formation of **1G** which was found as main product in our lignin depolymerization reactions.

Indeed, treating **S3** under the reaction conditions that were also used for lignin depolymerization, compound **1G** and the corresponding **2G** were found already after 30 minutes. Based on the reactivity of acetophenone above, **1G** was formed from **S3** via a rapid hydrogenation and dehydration/hydrogenation or direct hydrogenolysis. This experiment has also shown that the –OH group alpha to the aromatic ring was more prone to dehydration or direct hydrogenolysis under these reaction conditions, explaining the retention of the gamma –OH in **1G** in most lignin depolymerization runs. This experiment also explains the formation of **2G**, which is formed from **1G** likely via direct (and slower) hydrogenolysis. During these experiments the corresponding unsaturated intermediates were not observed, suggesting that the direct hydrogenolysis pathway operates, however their formation cannot be excluded at this point.

Finally, more complex model compounds **S4** and **S5** were tested and gave phenolic monomers with 4-propanol moiety as shown below.

Supplementary Note 3 Control experiments using pine lignocellulose

Control experiments were performed in a 25 mL Parr reactor following the procedure described in Supplementary Methods Section 3 and the full processing scheme is shown in Supplementary Fig. 81. After reaction the methanol soluble part was concentrated to 10 mL by evaporating part of the solvent and then transferred to a 15 mL centrifuge tube in which methanol was fully removed and the solids were dried in a desiccator until stable weight. Then solids were washed with 10 mL DCM (dichloromethane) and the suspensions were additionally treated in an ultrasonication bath to help solubilization. After centrifugation, the DCM soluble fraction was transferred to a round bottom flask. This process was repeated two times to remove all the DCM soluble products. The DCM was then removed from the combined washings. The DCM soluble products were analyzed by 2D NMR using CDCl₃. After solvent exchange to THF, these samples were additionally analyzed by Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). The DCM insoluble residues were dried and then analyzed by Eurovector (Euro EA 3000) Elemental Analyzer.

Supplementary Table 11 Fractionation of products after various control (Control 1-3) and one catalyzed (Cat 1) reaction using pine lignocellulose and the corresponding weights. (Entries Control 1 and Cat 1 are also shown in the main text, Fig. 2.)

Entries	Catalyst	Gas	Methanol-Soluble(g)	DCM Soluble(g)	DCM Insoluble(g)	Methanol-Insoluble(g) ^a	Mass Balance (%) ^b
Control 1	-	N ₂	0.13	0.105	0.026	0.79	92
Control 2	Cu20-PMO	N ₂	0.07	0.045	0.023	0.82	89
Control 3	Mg/Al-PMO	H ₂	0.08	0.045	0.026	0.80	88
Cat 1	Cu20-PMO	H ₂	0.08	0.061	0.016	0.80	88

Reaction conditions: Catalyst 0.2 g, Pine lignocellulose 1.0 g, methanol 10mL, 18h, 180 °C, H₂/N₂ 40 bar. a. Weight excludes catalyst. b. Mass balance = $(W_{\text{methanol-soluble}} + W_{\text{methanol-insoluble}}) / W_{\text{pine lignocellulose}}$

Supplementary Figure 81 Processing steps carried out during fractionation of methanol soluble products obtained after control reactions and one catalyzed reaction using pine lignocellulose.

Supplementary Figure 82 Comparison of GPC (Gel permeation chromatography) traces of the DCM soluble fractions of control reactions Control 1-Control 3 and one catalyzed reaction Cat 1 and pine organosolv lignin. Reaction conditions are shown in Supplementary Table 11.

Supplementary Table 12 Elemental analysis of pine lignocellulose and the DCM insoluble fractions of samples obtained during control and catalyzed reactions with pine lignocellulose.

Sample	Composition %		
	C	H	N
Control 1	50.55	5.92	0.22
Control 2	38.35	6.61	0.22
Control 3	36.50	6.03	0.15
Cat 1	46.36	7.29	0.32
Pine lignocellulose	42.74	6.19	0.05

Supplementary Note 4 Catalyst recycling tests

Catalyst recycling tests were carried out using pine lignocellulose. In a typical run 0.5 g pine lignocellulose and 0.2 g Cu₂O-PMO, 10 mL methanol was used (Step 1, mild). After that the solid residues were separated and fresh methanol was added and the mixture was heated to 320 °C (Step 2, supercritical). After that the content of the reactor was transferred to a centrifuge tube, and the methanol solution was separated from the solid (catalyst) by centrifugation and subsequent decantation. The solid was additionally washed with methanol (2 × 20 mL), then with acetone (1 × 20 mL), and dried overnight at room temperature in vacuum. The solid (catalyst) was then used in the next run as the same procedure (Step 1 and Step 2).

The products from Step 1 and Step 2 were both analyzed by GC-FID or GC-MS-FID. Summary of the results after each run are shown in Fig. 5 and Supplementary Table 13 and 14.

Leaching test:

1 mL of the solution obtained after reaction was transferred to a 10 mL glass vial, and the solvent was removed under vacuum. Aqua Regia was then added to the vial and the concentration of each metal was measured by Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV). The results were shown in Supplementary Table 15.

Supplementary Table 13 Results of mild depolymerization of pine lignocellulose (Step 1) during recycling tests.

Cycles	Catalyst (g)	Methanol Solubles (g) ^a	Methanol Insolubles (g) ^b	Monomers (mg) ^c				Monomer Yield (%) ^d	Monomer distribution
				1G	2G	3G	Sum		
1m	0.20	0.04	0.35	9	1	1	11	8	
2m	0.20	0.05	0.37	11	1	0	12	8	
3m	0.17	0.04	0.38	10	1	0	11	8	
4m	0.15	0.05	0.40	10	1	0	11	8	
5m	0.11	0.04	0.42	4	3	0	7	5	

Reaction conditions: Pine lignocellulose 0.5 g, methanol 10 mL, 180 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 18 h.

a. Weight of methanol soluble products excludes internal standard. b. Weight of methanol insoluble part excludes catalysts. c. Determined based on GC-FID measurement using calibration curves and internal standard. d. Monomer yield = weight_{monomers} / weight_{lignin}. The weight of lignin was determined as shown in Supplementary Methods Section 7 and Supplementary Table 5.

1G: Dihydroconiferyl alcohol, **2G**: 4-Propylguaiacol, **3G**: 4-Ethylguaiacol.

Supplementary Table 14 Conversion of the solid residues obtained from pine lignocellulose in supercritical methanol (Step 2) from different cycles and selectivity of the products by groups.

Cycles ^a	Conversion (%) ^b	Selectivity (%) ^c									
		A	A'	HE	HE'	ET	ET'	ES	ES'	OT	
1s	100	63.5	3.3	5.5	0	3.8	2.0	1.9	0.9	19.1	
2s	100	60.1	1.6	8.5	0.5	1.7	1.6	2.0	0.5	23.5	
3s	100	66.9	1.1	6.6	0.2	2.9	0.8	1.9	1.5	18.1	
4s	100	38.1	7.7	6.2	0.6	0	1.9	1.8	2.0	41.7	
5s	94	7.8	2.7	4.6	0	0	0.5	35.9	1.8	46.7	

■ Alcohols
 ■ Hydroxy Ethers
 ■ Ethers
 ■ Esters
 ■ Phenolics
 ■ Others/unidentified

a. 6h for 1st and 2nd cycles and 8 h for 3-5 cycles. b. conversion calculated based on the weight of the remaining solid residue. c. selectivity calculated based on GC-FID analysis; Explanation of groups: A: alcohols with high quality match (≥ 70%); A': alcohols with low quality match (30%-70%); HE: hydroxyl ethers with high quality match (≥ 70%); HE': hydroxyl ethers with low quality match (30%-70%); ET: ethers with high quality match (≥ 70%); ET': ethers with low quality match (30%-70%); ES: esters with high quality match (≥ 70%); ES': esters with low quality match (30%-70%); OT: others.

Supplementary Table 15 Leaching tests during catalyst recycling for Cu₂O-PMO catalyst.

Cycles	Cu (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	Al (mg/L)	Cu (%) ^a	Mg (%)	Al (%)
1m	1	4	2	0.03	0.08	0.09
1s	2	11	2	0.08	0.28	0.11
4m	3	2	2	0.10	0.04	0.09
4s	29	3	4	1.13	0.08	0.21
1m ^b	3	17	3	0.10	0.35	0.13

a. percentages refer to the total initial mass of the individual element in the catalyst. b. Separate experiment carried out for 36 hours reaction time.

Supplementary Note 5 Coupling of cyclopentanone using 1-pentanol as model compound

Cyclopentanone has a cyclic structure and can be derived from lignocellulosic biomass.^{5–10} Furfural is exclusively produced from renewable agricultural waste sources such as food crop residues. Due to the increased demand, the furfural market volume is projected to be ~0.5 Mt annually with an estimated annual growth rate of 4.3%, while its price has been in the range of \$900–1000 per ton.¹¹ Nowadays bioethanol (producer price) is around 0.6\$ per liter (density: 789kg/m³), which means 1267 \$ per ton in contrast with the price of furfural between 900-1000\$ per ton.¹² Furfural can be quantitatively transformed to cyclopentanone using heterogeneous catalysts, through scalable procedures^{8,13} with excellent 82% atom economy, whereby all carbon atoms are incorporated into the product and water is the only byproduct. Therefore, cyclopentanone is a very appealing coupling partner.

Recently, it was found that cyclopentanone can be used as a potential building block for the synthesis of diesel and jet-fuel range cycloalkanes^{14–19}. For example, from the hydroxyalkylation/alkylation (HAA) of cyclopentanone with 2-methylfuran followed by hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) a mixture of C9-C15 branched alkanes and cycloalkanes can be produced.¹⁵ It was also reported that high-density (0.82 g mL⁻¹) jet-fuel range cycloalkanes can be synthesized in high overall yields (~80%) by the aldol condensation of cyclopentanone and butanal followed by hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) reaction.¹⁷

Based on these pioneering literature studies, we envisioned that our **SMix1** products which comprise mainly aliphatic alcohols can also be used in the coupling reaction with cyclopentanone. First, we have employed 1-pentanol as a suitable model compound to establish suitable reaction conditions for the formation of a carbon-carbon bond between cyclopentanone and pentanol. The following sequence of steps was proposed: 1-pentanol is first dehydrogenated to 1-pentanal and subsequently undergoes aldol condensation with cyclopentanone facilitated by the basic sites of the PMO catalyst. The product of the aldol condensation would then undergo hydrogenation to the corresponding saturated ketone via the hydrogen generated in the first dehydrogenation step.

First, we have used Mg/Al-PMO that are known to be solid base catalyst for a variety of aldol condensation reactions and were also used in similar transformations involving acetone and furfural as well as primary alcohols and furfural.^{20–25}

The results of this screening are shown in entries 1-5, Supplementary Table 16 below. While a good conversion of 1-pentanol was seen, relatively low 2-pentylcyclopentanone selectivity was obtained due to the self-coupling of cyclopentanone which produced [1,1'-bi(cyclopentan)]-2-one as the main product. Changing of temperature didn't influence the conversion and selectivity, and increasing the relative amount of 1-pentanol did not sufficiently increase product selectivity. We have then selected a porous metal oxide that containing both Cu and Ni dopants and was developed in our laboratory for the highly selective Guerbet reaction of ethanol to 1-butanol.²⁶ Gratifyingly, this catalyst provided much better results in the coupling of 1-pentanol with cyclopentanone (Supplementary Table 16, entry 6).

Supplementary Table 16 Coupling of 1-pentanol with cyclopentanone at different reaction conditions.

Entry	Catalyst	Cyclopentanone (mmol)	1-Pentanol (mmol)	Temperature (°C)	Conversion of 1-pentanol (%)	GC selectivity (%) ^a
1	PMO	1.1	0.46	150	89	12.4
2	PMO	1.1	0.46	180	84	9.8
3	PMO	1.1	0.46	200	76	12.9
4	PMO	1.1	0.92	180	44	10.2
5	PMO	0.55	0.92	180	40	25.5
6	CuNi-PMO	0.55	0.92	180	63	61.9

Reaction conditions: heptane 3 mL, catalyst 0.05 g, dodecane 10 μ L, 18h.

a. selectivity of 2-pentylcyclopentanone based on GC area percentage.

Supplementary Note 6 Coupling of cyclopentanone with a mixture of selected model alcohols

After establishing ideal reaction conditions with 1-pentanol, a mixture of model alcohols that are representative for the composition of **SMix1** (obtained from lignocellulose processing) was prepared. In a flask, 10 different aliphatic alcohols including ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 2-butanol, 2-methyl-1-propanol, 2-methyl-1-butanol, 2-methyl-1-pentanol, cyclohexanol and 2-methylcyclohexanol with equal volume of 1 mL were mixed. In a typical experiment, 0.1 mL of the solution of model alcohols (1.07 mmol total alcohols) and 0.05 mL (0.55 mmol) cyclopentanone were placed in the microreactor and heptane (3 mL) was added as solvent. Then 100 mg catalyst was added, the reactor was sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at 180 °C. After 24 hours, the microreactor was cooled down in an ice-water bath and the liquid sample was separated by filtration. The collected samples were then analyzed by GC-MS.

Supplementary Figure 83 GC-MS chromatogram of the products obtained after coupling of cyclopentanone with the model alcohol mixture. Reaction conditions: alcohol mixtures 0.1 mL (1.07 mmol), cyclopentanone 0.05 mL (0.55 mmol), CuNi-PMO 0.1 g, heptane 3 mL, 180 °C, 24 h.

Under the established reaction conditions, efficient coupling of the long chain primary alcohols with cyclopentanone was observed. The linear primary alcohols coupled preferentially 1:1 with cyclopentanone, resulting in C7-C10 ketones, but coupling of 2 equivalents of these primary alcohols with 1 equivalent of cyclopentanone was also seen, resulting in C11-C15 ketones. Interestingly, a reaction between cyclopentanone as well as methyl-cyclohexanol with cyclohexanol was also observed. Self-coupling products of cyclopentanone were also seen. Branched 2-methyl-1-pentanol

as well as the cyclic cyclohexanol and methyl-cyclohexanol albeit partially dehydrogenated, did not undergo efficient coupling reaction due to steric hindrance.

Determining that efficient coupling occurred with most linear alcohols and establishing good analytical practices, we have moved towards optimization reactions using the **SMix1** directly as described below.

Supplementary Note 7 Coupling of cyclopentanone with alcohol mixtures (**SMix 1**) from step 2

We have performed a solvent exchange from methanol to heptane prior to coupling of the alcohols obtained from pine lignocellulose with cyclopentanone. This was necessary because methanol solvent hampered efficient coupling reaction.

Supplementary Figure 84 GC-FID chromatograms of the solvent exchange procedure. Upper: **SMix1** solution in methanol; Middle: Heptane solution after distillation of methanol showing that most aliphatic alcohols remained in heptane; Down: Methanol solution showing negligible amount of alcohols.

Supplementary Figure 85 GC-MS chromatogram of the heptane insoluble oil (~30 mg). Based on the analysis of GC-MS, the heptane insoluble oil contains mainly alcohols and small amount of ethers, esters and phenolics.

Since the coupling of the alcohol products contained in the **SMix1** generated from pine lignocellulose with cyclopentanone under previously established reaction conditions at 180 °C did not deliver sufficient yields of longer chain ketones, we increased the temperature to 250 °C and subsequently increased the catalyst loading. These reaction conditions delivered very good selectivity of the

desired long chain ketones. Most of the main products were identified by GC-MS measurements and also described in Supplementary Table 17. Due to the complexity of the mixtures obtained, the quantification of the products was performed in great detail after the hydrodeoxygenation reaction described in Supplementary Note 9.

Supplementary Figure 86 GC-MS chromatograms of the products obtained upon coupling of cyclopentanone with the alcohols from pine solid residue **SMix 1**. Reaction conditions: cyclopentanone 0.05 mL (0.55 mmol), heptane 3 mL, 24 h.

Supplementary Table 17 Complete overview of GC-MS signals, identification of products after coupling of cyclopentanone with **SMix1** (Supplementary Fig. 86)

Peak	Time (minutes)	Area	Area %	Identification	Quality match %
1	5.581	70306867	7.91	Cyclopentanol	86
2	5.681	97538775	11.01	Cyclopentanone	84
3	7.942	26779749	3.01	Cyclopentanone, 3-methyl-	98

4	8.025	49907679	5.62	Cyclopentanone, 2-methyl-	98
5	8.282	74136530	8.34	Cyclopentanol, 2-methyl-	95
6	10.797	20024487	2.25	Cyclopentanone, 2,5-dimethyl-	91
7	10.964	34980102	3.94	2,4-Dimethylcyclopentanol	82
8	11.106	15089374	1.7	Cyclopentanone, 2,5-dimethyl-	88
9	11.441	11465207	1.29	Cyclohexanone, 4-methyl-	75
10	11.888	10365255	1.17	Cyclohexanol, 3-methyl-	72
11	13.286	27773523	3.13	Cyclopentanone, 2-ethyl-	87
12	13.451	14256193	1.6	Cyclohexanol, 2-methyl-	87
13	13.995	11291908	1.27	3-Methyl-2-butenic acid, 2-tetrahydrofurylmethyl ester	76
14	15.326	21001087	2.36	Not identified	-
15	16.271	61152266	6.88	2-Propylcyclopentanone	86
16	18.46	35753812	4.02	Cyclopentanone, 2-(1-methylpropyl)-	86
17	20.189	11336553	1.28	not identified	-
18	20.348	39105599	4.4	2-Butylcyclopentanone	85
19	20.649	59548455	6.7	4,4,6-Trimethyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-ol	76
20	20.7	9570838	1.08	1,2-Cycloheptanediol	80
21	22.259	18008657	2.03	not identified	-
22	22.362	12118367	1.36	not identified	-
23	23.078	23534159	2.65	2-Pentylcyclopentanone	87
24	23.78	11981747	1.35	2-Naphthalenol, decahydro-	78
25	23.845	46826910	5.27	[1,1'-Bicyclopentyl]-2-one	92
26	24.414	10063740	1.13	Benzene, 4-ethyl-1,2-dimethoxy-	77
27	24.498	4006788	0.45	not identified	-
28	24.714	10006871	1.13	2-Hexylcyclopentanone	74
29	24.898	6703457	0.75	2-butyl-5-propylcyclopentanone	a
30	25.033	7140634	0.8	Cyclopentanone, 2-(5-oxohexyl)-	69
31	25.489	19758699	2.22	1,2-Dimethoxy-4-n-propylbenzene	a
32	25.914	7507635	0.85	2-(3-methylcyclohexyl)cyclopentanone	a
33	26.223	9368872	1.05	2,5-dibutylcyclopentanone	a

a. peaks were identified based on molecular weight and comparison with the results from model compound study.

Supplementary Note 8 Hydrodeoxygenation of the ketones obtained from the coupling of **SMix1** with cyclopentanone to alkanes

Based on literature studies that employed Ni/SiO_2 ¹⁷ and $\text{Ni}/\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ¹⁵ catalyst for the hydrodeoxygenation of ketones to alkanes, we have selected the commercially available $\text{Ni}/\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ to establish our method for the efficient hydrodeoxygenation of the mixtures of ketones obtained upon coupling of lignocellulose derived aliphatic alcohols contained in **SMix1**. Then, we have used the mixtures of ketones obtained upon the coupling of the selected, standard mixture of alcohols with cyclopentanone as described in Supplementary Note 6. Full hydrodeoxygenation was seen and clear mixtures of alkanes in heptane were obtained. Next, we used these established reaction conditions to perform hydrodeoxygenation on the ketones obtained after coupling with **SMix1** described in Supplementary Note 7. Full conversion of the ketones was seen. Also the shorter aliphatic alcohols and ketones that did not undergo coupling reaction underwent efficient HDO to alkanes. The heptane insoluble oil also underwent efficient HDO to alkanes.

Supplementary Figure 87 Recycling test of catalytic HDO by $\text{Ni}/\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ using 4-propylcyclohexanone as model compound. Reaction conditions: 4-propylcyclohexanone 1.5 mmol, heptane 10 mL, $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ 0.2 g, 250 °C, 6 h, H_2 40 bar. Note: the substrate amount was increased after 11 cycles.

Supplementary Figure 88 GC-MS chromatogram of the products obtained after hydrodeoxygenation of a product mixture obtained upon coupling of selected model alcohols with cyclopentanone. Reaction conditions: heptane solution 10 mL, Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ 0.2 g, 250 °C, 6 h, H₂ 40 bar.

Supplementary Figure 89 GC-MS chromatogram of the products obtained after hydrodeoxygenation of a product mixture obtained upon coupling of **SMix1** (transferred to heptane) with cyclopentanone. Reaction conditions: heptane solution 10 mL, Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ 0.2 g, 250 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 6 h, eicosane 20 mg.

Supplementary Figure 90 GC-MS chromatogram of the products obtained after hydrodeoxygenation when using the heptane insoluble oil. Reaction conditions: heptane solution 10 mL, Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ 0.2 g, 250 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 6 h, eicosane 20 mg.

Supplementary Figure 91 GC-FID chromatogram of the products obtained after hydrodeoxygenation when using a product mixture obtained upon coupling of **SMix1** (transferred to heptane) with cyclopentanone. The inserted figure shows the comparison of the range of short alkanes when cooling to room temperature versus 0 °C after reaction. Reaction conditions: heptane solution 10 mL, Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ 0.2 g, 250 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 6 h, eicosane 20 mg.

Supplementary Table 18 Distribution of the products after hydrodeoxygenation based on chain length.^a

Entry ^b	Weight (mg)							Total Alkanes	C8+ Alkanes
	C4	C5	C6	C8	C9	C10	C11+ ^c		
1	29.1	101.6	30.1	26.0	20.2	20.3	5.7	233.0	72.2
2	33.7	118.4	37.5	21.3	15.7	21.9	10.7	259.2	69.6
3	3.6	5.1	1.6	6.2	1.3	1.2	2.1	21.2	10.8
2+3	40.9	119.9	39.1	27.8	17.0	23.1	12.8	280.4	80.5
Carbon content (mg) ^d									
1	24.1	84.5	25.2	22.3	17.3	17.4	4.9	195.7	61.9
2	27.9	98.5	31.4	18.2	13.4	18.7	9.2	217.3	59.5
3	3.0	4.2	1.3	5.3	1.1	1.0	1.8	17.7	9.2
2+3	30.9	102.7	32.7	23.5	14.5	19.7	11.0	235.0	68.7

a. Due to the overlap with heptane, alkanes in the C7 chain length range cannot be calculated, thus the current numbers are an underestimation of the actual carbon yield. b. Entry 1 shows the results using the heptane solubles and cooling to room temperature after HDO reaction, Entry 2 shows the results using heptane solubles and cooling to 0 °C by ice water after HDO reaction, Entry 3 shows the results using heptane insolubles and cooling to 0 °C by ice water after HDO reaction, c. Calculated as C15. d. For the carbon content in alkanes we use chemical formula C_nH_{2n+2} for C4, C5 and C6 as they are mainly linear or branched alkanes and C_nH_{2n} for C8+ as they are mainly cyclic alkanes. So the carbon content in entry 2 of C6 is 31.4 mg ($37.5 \times 83.6\%$) and C10 is 18.7 mg ($21.9 \times 85.6\%$).

After hydrodeoxygenation, small amount of butane and other volatile alkanes are detectable by GC-MS and GC-FID. Since the solubility of these is highly dependent of the temperature²⁷ the reaction was repeated by cooling the reactor to 0 °C with ice water. Compare Entry 1 to Entry 2, cooling the reactor substantially increased the yield of C4 alkanes.

Supplementary Note 9 Determination of the yield of alkanes

In order to calculate the yield of alkanes obtained after hydrodeoxygenation, internal standard eicosane (C₂₀H₄₂) was added after reaction. Sensitivity factors of the products were obtained by ECN-based calculations due to lack of commercial standards.²⁸

The weight of alkanes of different chain length (W_x) was calculated based on the equation:

$$W_x = \frac{C_{20} \cdot A_x \cdot W_{20} \cdot M_x}{C_x \cdot A_{20} \cdot M_{20}}$$

M_x: molar mass of the alkanes with certain chain length; C_x: carbon number of the alkanes with certain chain length; A_x: summary of peak areas of products have the same chain length. C₂₀: carbon number of internal standard; A₂₀: area of internal standard; W₂₀: weight of internal standard; M₂₀: molar mass of internal standard.

The carbon content of the solid residue and obtained alkanes was calculated as below

The weight of the solid residue was determined experimentally. From the analysis as described in Supplementary Methods Section 7, 1 g pine lignocellulose contains 286 mg lignin. We assumed that the solid residue (in total 790 mg) contains 714 mg carbohydrates, and the rest is unconverted lignin (76 mg). We further assumed that the chemical structure of the carbohydrates is described by that of cellulose (main component), a regular polymer consisting of glucose units.

The percentage of carbon in (C₆H₁₀O₅)_n is therefore 44.4%. We used the basic phenol monomer coniferyl alcohol described by the chemical formula (C₁₀H₁₂O₃)_n as main building block describing the unreacted lignin component.

The carbon percentage is therefore 66.7%. As a result the carbon content in solid residue is 368 mg (714×44.4%+76×66.7%).

Supplementary Note 10 Catalytic conversion of **1G** to **4**

We set out to study the direct reaction of the aliphatic alcohol moiety of **1G** with ammonia directly using heterogeneous Ni catalysts.^{29–31} We envisioned that a Ni based heterogeneous catalyst will affect the dehydrogenation of the alcohol to the corresponding aldehyde, which will undergo condensation with ammonia to form the corresponding imine. The primary amine can then be generated by a “borrowing hydrogen” sequence or the imine can undergo further dehydrogenation to the corresponding nitrile (see Supplementary Fig. 92). Being aware that the key issue is product selectivity, we have first used a variety of heterogeneous Ni catalyst to elucidate ideal catalyst composition. Among the tested catalysts, Cu-Zn alloy, CuNi-PMO and Ni/C showed no substrate conversion under these reaction conditions. Raney Ni displayed good to excellent substrate conversion, however poor selectivity and delivered a mixture of different products including the expected nitrile as well as primary amine and secondary amine (Supplementary Table 19). Additional products observed were **2G**, obtained upon direct hydrogenolysis or dehydration/hydrogenation of **1G**; and **3G**, which likely formed upon decarbonylation of the aldehyde (see also Supplementary Fig. 92). Compared to Raney Ni, Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ was less active but displayed much better selectivity towards 3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)propanenitrile (**4**).

Supplementary Table 19 Screening different catalysts for the transformation of **1G** to the corresponding amines and nitrile.

Entry	Catalysts	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	GC Yield (%)				
				2G	3G	4	5	5DA
1	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	4	42.5	0.6	3.2	18.2	18.9	1.6
2	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	18	86.6	5.9	11.9	28.1	28.7	12.0
3	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	24	91.9	7.9	13.4	23.6	32.6	14.5
4	Raney Ni	4	61.3	2.1	13.1	4.3	37.9	5.0
5	Raney Ni	18	93.2	11.1	33.1	5.6	29.2	14.3
6	Raney Ni	24	97.6	13.8	33.1	12.3	25.2	13.2
7	Cu-Zn alloy	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Ni/C	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	Cu-Ni-PMO	18	0	0	0	0	0	0

Reaction conditions: a. Raney Ni (0.1 g wet) or other catalysts 0.05 g, NH₃-THF (0.5 M) 3 mL, substrate 0.09 g (0.5 mmol), 180 °C, NH₃:substrate = 3:1.

2G: 4-Propylguaiacol; **3G**: 4-Ethylguaiacol; **4**: 4-Propanenitrileguaiacol; **5**: 4-(3-aminopropyl)guaiacol; **5DA**: 4,4'-(azanediylbis(propane-3,1-diyl))bis(2-methoxyphenol).

Supplementary Figure 92 Proposed reaction mechanism for catalytic conversion of **1G** to **4** via dehydrogenation and amination reaction.

Therefore we have selected the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst for further optimization of reaction conditions to get higher yield of nitrile **4** (Supplementary Table 20). First, we increased the NH₃ to substrate ratio in order to facilitate the imine formation pathway and thereby suppress the formation of 4-ethylguaiaicol (**3G**) by decarbonylation. To our surprise, when the NH₃ to substrate ratio increased from 3 to 10, we observed the formation of **4** in perfect selectivity, albeit at lower conversion 12%. Therefore, we increased the reaction time and further increased the NH₃ amount. Finally **4** was obtained in very good selectivity (about 90%) at full conversion. This reaction was repeated 4 times (limitations existed due to the small volume of the microreactor) and the pure product **4** was isolated in 69% yield. This reaction was also performed under Argon atmosphere, without obvious differences in product selectivity and conversion showing that oxygen likely did not affect the reaction, thus a true dehydrogenation of both the alcohol **1G** as well as the imine intermediate took place.

Supplementary Table 20 Optimization of reaction conditions for the transformation of **1G** to **4**.

Entry	Catalyst (g)	Solvent (mL)	NH ₃ :Substrate	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	GC Yield (%)			
						2G	3G	4	5
1	0.01	2	10	16	12.0	0	0	12.0	0
2	0.01	2	10	60	100	4.1	7.2	30.1	24.4
3	0.02	3	15	16	68.1	2.7	7.5	57.8(37%) ^a	0
4	0.02	4	15	16	59.2	2.2	7.1	47.7	0
5	0.02	5	15	16	54.4	1.9	6.6	41.3	0
6	0.02	4	20	20	100	2.7	8.7	88.6	0
7 ^b	0.02	4	20	24	100	3.4	6.3	87.9 (69%) ^c	0
8 ^d	0.02	4	20	24	100	1.2	7.4	80.7(64%) ^c	0
9 ^e	0.02	4	20	24	100	1.8	7.2	86.3	0

Reaction conditions: NH_3 -THF (0.5 M), substrate 0.02 g (0.1 mmol), 180 °C. a. isolated yield. b. reaction repeated for 4 times and give an average number. c. isolated yield from 4 reactions. d. using isolated **1G** as starting material. e. reaction under Ar.

2G: 4-Propylguaiacol; **3G**: 4-Ethylguaiacol; **4**: 4- Propanenitrileguaiacol; **5**: 4-(3-aminopropyl)guaiacol.

Supplementary Note 11 Selective conversion of nitrile **4** and **1G**

Since nitrile **4** was obtained in excellent selectivity, it could be further catalytically converted to the derivatives also shown on Supplementary Fig. 13, using the same Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst simply by changing the reaction conditions. Hydrogenation at 110 °C provided the desired primary amine in very good selectivity and high purity. It should be noted, that such good selectivity could not be achieved despite several attempts though a “borrowing hydrogen” manner when using alcohol **1G** directly due to the inevitable competing reaction involving the formation of the corresponding secondary amine typical for such reactions. Next, dehydrogenation and decarbonylation of the alcohol without addition of ammonia resulted in the selective formation of compound **3G**. To provide evidence for a decarbonylation pathway and the existence of the aldehyde as crucial intermediate in our reaction pathways, we performed dehydrogenation of **1G** over the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst in the presence of ethylene glycol. Gratifyingly, the aldehyde intermediate was captured in the form of its ethylene glycol acetal as well as a small amount of aldehyde itself as shown on Supplementary Fig. 93.

Supplementary Table 21 Catalytic conversion of **1G** to **3G** and **4** to **5**

Entry	Substrate	Time (h)	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Conversion (%)	GC-Yield%
1 ^a	1G	18	Toluene	220	100	84(75) ^b
2 ^c	1G	18	Toluene	220	100	77(75) ^b
3 ^d	4	5	Methanol	110	100	98(95) ^b

a. Reaction conditions: solvent 3 mL, substrate 20 mg, catalyst 10 mg. b. Average numbers from 4 identical reactions and the number in brackets is the isolated yield from combined 4 reactions. c. using **1G** isolated from lignocellulose as the starting material. d. Reaction conditions: solvent 1.7 mL, substrate (44 mg), catalyst (10 mg), H₂ (20 bar).

Supplementary Figure 93 GC-MS chromatogram of products after reaction of **1G** in presence of ethylene glycol.

Reaction conditions: toluene 3 mL, catalyst (10 mg), substrate (90 mg, 0.5 mmol), ethylene glycol (0.1 mL, 1.8 mmol), 220 °C, 18 h.

Supplementary Note 12 Catalytic conversion of Syringol-type monomers

In Supplementary Methods Section 12 only Guaiacol-type monomers are shown as starting materials. However hardwoods normally produce more Syringol-type monomers, therefore it is necessary to evaluate their reactivity as well. Therefore, **1S** and **3S** were used as starting materials in this part. Reaction conditions analogous to those established in Supplementary Methods Section 12 were used.

As shown in figure above, firstly compound **1S** was isolated from the mild depolymerization of maple lignocellulose (Supplementary Table 2, Entry 6) and was readily converted to **3S** with 79% isolated yield.

Due to the limited amount of **3S**, further screening was performed using **3S** synthesized from Acetosyringone (Supplementary Methods Section 6).

Supplementary Note 13 Existing applications of the obtained compounds

1G can be used for the synthesis of **XH-14**, which has been widely used in China for the treatment of coronary heart disease.³² It can also be used for the synthesis of novel epoxy resins. For example, van de Pas and co-workers reported using hydrogenolysis products derived from softwood lignin (which contain mainly **1G**) as replacements for BADGE in new epoxy thermosetting polymers.³³

Based on the strategy developed by Sels and co-workers, **3G** can be converted to 4-ethylcyclohexanol by supported Ni catalysts and then dehydrogenated to 4-ethylcyclohexanone with high yield.^{34,35} Finally the alkylated ϵ -caprolactone (precursors for novel polymer building blocks) can be produced by Sn-beta zeolite in high yields, by a Baeyer–Villiger-type oxidation.³⁵ **3G** can be also used for the production of bisphenol polymer precursors like 5,5'-methylenebis(4-ethylguaiacol).³⁶ The corresponding bisphenols can be polymerized to polycarbonates, cyanate esters and epoxy resins.^{37,38} Abu-Omar and co-workers performed in-depth research for the application of lignin

derived monomers. Based on their results, lignin-derived 4-alkylguaiacols can be used for the production of biobased epoxy nanocomposites³⁹, renewable thermoplastics⁴⁰ and renewable thermoset polymers⁴¹.

Compound **6** is a versatile polymer building block. It can be functionalized with epoxy, cyclic carbonates, allyl, amine, alcohol and carboxylic acid moieties.⁴² Through transesterification of compound **6** with bio-based polyols in the presence of a lipase, different bisphenol building blocks can be obtained for polyester synthesis.⁴³ **6** can also be used for preparing the aromatic polyester poly(dihydroferulic acid), which exhibits thermal properties functionally similar to those of polyethylene terephthalate (PET).⁴⁴ Besides polymer building blocks, compound **6** has potential to be used as pharma intermediate. For example, **JBIR-94** was isolated from the culture broth of a new species of *Streptomyces* (strain R56-07) and it represents potential lead compounds in the development of a series of novel biologically active molecules with antioxidant and other useful properties.^{45,46}

Through demethylation reaction, compound **6** could also be converted to corresponding catechol to be used for new mussel-inspired polymer materials.⁴⁷

Compound **6Cy** is a pharma intermediate, which can be easily obtained from **6**. For instance, it can be turned into Donepezil using commercially available reagents.⁴⁸ The derived 1-indanone thiosemicarbazone derivatives also show potent anti-viral activity.⁴⁹

Styrene analogue **7** was used for the synthesis of functionalized polystyrene materials.^{50,51} For example Takeshima et al. synthesized a series of well-defined bio-based poly(vinylguaiacol) with phenolic functions. Besides polymer building blocks Araki et al. developed pharmacological applications.⁵² **7S** was synthesized from **7** by metathesis reaction, through transesterification of this bisphenol with diphenyl carbonate a polycarbonate can be obtained.⁵³ Further functionalization leads to photoresponsive supramolecular polymers.⁵⁴ Epoxy phenolic dimers can also be easily synthesized and used to make epoxy resins.⁵⁵

Supplementary Note 14 Potential applications of the obtained compounds

Vanillin alcohol had shown potential to be used in epoxy, polyester, polyurethane, and non-isocyanate polyurethane polymer synthesis⁴². Due to similar structure **1G** may be used as polymer building blocks after analogous functionalization. **1G** can be also used for the synthesis of sustainable bisphenols by coupling with diamine or di-acid chloride.

By direct functionalization of the phenol group of **3G**, 4-ethyl-2-methoxybenzenamine (**12b**) and its derivatives are successfully obtained. Among them, **9b** and **12b** may be used for the synthesis of anti-tumor compounds Arctigenin (ATG).⁵⁶

Compound **12c** could find use in medicinal chemistry.⁵⁷

Compounds **5** and **13** could directly react with acryloyl chloride and then incorporated into thermoplastic polymers by the radical polymerization.⁵⁸

Supplementary Methods

1. Materials and equipment

Chemicals were used as received, unless otherwise specified. Pine lignocellulose was purchased from Bemap Houtmeel B.V., lignocellulose from other resources were obtained from a local wood shop (Dikhout, Groningen, the Netherlands).

Reagents: triethylamine, glycine methyl ester hydrochloride, amines: pyrazole, 3,5-dimethylpyrazole, pyrrolidine, octylamine, nonylamine, dibutylamine, morpholine, aniline, cyclohexylamine, benzylamine, ethylamine solution (10% in THF), methylamine solution (40% in MeOH), 1-ethylpropylamine, 4-aminophenol, 4-chloroaniline, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenylenediamine, *N*-benzylmethylamine, *N*-ethylaniline, α -methylbenzylamine, 2-pyrrolidinone, 3-ethyl-4-methylaniline, *o*-anisidine, *m*-anisidine, piperidine, vinyl acetate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich; Ammonia solution (0.5M in THF), (diacetoxyiodo)benzene, cesium fluoride were purchased from Acros Organics; dihydroconiferyl alcohol, diethylcarbonyl chloride, sodium *tert*-butoxide, 2,2'-bipyridyl were purchased from TCI.

Catalysts and catalyst precursors: Ni precursor bis(1,5-cyclooctadiene)nickel(0) for the cross coupling reactions and (oxydi-2,1-phenylene)bis(diphenylphosphine) were purchased from Strem Chemicals, Inc.; Raney Ni and Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalysts, Hoveyda-Grubbs catalyst 2nd generation, dichloro(*p*-cymene)ruthenium(II) dimer, tetrakis(acetonitrile)copper(I) tetrafluoroborate, TEMPO, ligands 1,3-bis-(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazolium chloride used for the cross coupling reactions, AlCl₃·6H₂O, Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich; MgCl₂·6H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O were purchased from ACROS Organics. Tricyclohexylphosphine, palladium(II) chloride were purchased from TCI.

Solvents: Toluene was collected from a MBRAUN solvent purification system (MB SPS-800). Methyl alcohol (MeOH, 99%), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP, 99%), dimethyl carbonate (DMC, 99%) and acetonitrile (CH₃CN, 99.9%, extra dry) were purchased from Acros without further purification.

Chromatography: TLC and column chromatography: Merck silica gel type 9385 230-400 mesh. TLC: Merck silica gel 60, 0.25 mm. Components were visualized by UV, KMnO₄ staining.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) was performed on a Hewlett Packard 1100 system equipped with three PL-gel 3 μ m MIXED-E columns in series. The columns were operated at 42 °C with a flow-rate of 1 mL/min of THF. Detection was accomplished at 35 °C using a GBC LC 1240 RI detector. The molecular weight estimations were performed using polystyrene standards of known molecular weight distribution.

Gas chromatography with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) was performed using a Hewlett Packard 6890 series equipped with a HP-5 capillary column using nitrogen as carrier gas. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was performed using a Shimadzu GC-2010 plus system equipped with a GCMS QP2010 GC SE detector and a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μ m). Some samples were also analyzed by GC-MS-FID (Hewlett Packard 5890) equipped with a Restek RTX-1701 capillary column.

Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI-MS-902 mass spectrometer (EI⁺) or a LTQ Orbitrap XL (ESI⁺).

NMR spectroscopy: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian AMX400 (400 and 101 MHz, respectively) using CDCl_3 or CD_3OD as solvent at room temperature. Chemical shift values are reported in ppm with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (CDCl_3 : 7.26 for ^1H , 77.16 for ^{13}C ; CD_3OD : 3.31 for ^1H , 49.00 for ^{13}C). Data are reported as follows: chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, br. = broad, m = multiplet), coupling constants (Hz), and integration.

2D NMR spectroscopy: The 2D-HSQC NMR was recorded in CDCl_3 or $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$ using a reported pulse sequence on Varian AMX400 at room temperature.⁵⁹ Identification and integration of the signals were performed using literature reports.^{59,60}

2. Preparation and characterization of PMO catalysts

The HTC (hydrotalcite) catalyst precursors were prepared by a co-precipitation method, according to literature⁶¹. The catalyst prepared in this procedure is named as Cu20-PMO in which 20% of the Mg²⁺ ions were replaced with Cu²⁺ ions in a 3:1 Mg/Al hydrotalcite precursor.

In a typical procedure, a solution containing AlCl₃·6H₂O (12.07 g, 0.05 mol), Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O (6.98 g, 0.03 mol) and MgCl₂·6H₂O (24.40 g, 0.12 mol) in deionized water (0.2 L) was added to a solution containing Na₂CO₃ (5.30 g, 0.05 mol) in water (0.3 L) at 60 °C under vigorous stirring. The pH was kept between 9 and 10 by addition of small portions of a 1 M solution of NaOH. The mixture was vigorously stirred at 60 °C for 72 h. After cooling to room temperature, the light blue solid was filtered and resuspended in a 2 M solution of Na₂CO₃ (0.3 L) and stirred overnight at 40°C. The catalyst precursor was filtered and washed with deionized water until chloride free. After drying the solid for 6 h at 100 °C, 15.07 g of the hydrotalcite (HTC) was obtained. Before use, 4 g of hydrotalcite was calcined at 460 °C for 24 h in air and 2.5 g of Cu20-PMO can be obtained.

The Mg/Al-PMO catalyst (without any dopants) was prepared using AlCl₃·6H₂O (12.07 g, 0.05 mol) and MgCl₂·6H₂O (30.50 g, 0.15 mol) following the same procedure as above and 15.3 g Mg/Al-HTC was obtained. Before use, 3 g of this hydrotalcite was calcined to yield about 2 g Mg/Al-PMO catalyst.

The CuNi-PMO was prepared using Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O (0.02 mol, 4.65 g), Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (0.01 mol, 2.9 g), AlCl₃·6H₂O (12.07 g, 0.05 mol) and MgCl₂·6H₂O (24.40 g, 0.12 mol) based on the same procedure and 15.5 g CuNi-HTC was obtained. Before use, 3 g of this hydrotalcite was calcined to yield 2.2 g CuNi-PMO catalyst.

Powder X-ray analysis was performed on a Bruker XRD diffractometer using Cu K α radiation and the spectra were recorded in the 2 θ angle range of 5°-70°. Elemental analysis was performed on a Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV). The textural characterization was achieved using conventional nitrogen adsorption/desorption method, with a Micromeritics ASAP 2420 automatic analyzer. Prior to nitrogen adsorption, the samples were outgassed for 8 h at 250 °C. The Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method was used for the calculating of pore volume and average pore size. TEM measurements were performed on a FEI Tecnai T20 electron microscope. Elemental distribution was measured in STEM mode using a HAADF detector and an X-max 80 EDX detector (Oxford instruments).

3. Mild depolymerization of pine lignocellulose

The mild depolymerization of pine lignocellulose was carried out in a 25 mL or 100 mL high pressure Parr autoclave with an overhead stirrer. Typically, the autoclave was charged with Cu₂O-PMO catalyst (0.2 g), pine lignocellulose (1 g), 3,5-dimethylphenol (20 mg as internal standard) and methanol (10 mL). The reactor was sealed and pressurized with H₂ (40 bar) at room temperature. The reactor was heated to 180 °C and stirred at 400 rpm for 18 h. After reaction, the reactor was cooled to room temperature. Then 0.1 mL solution was collected with syringe and injected to GC-MS or GC-FID after filtration with a PTFE filter (0.42 μm). After that the solution and solids were transferred into a 50 mL centrifuge tube. The solid was separated from the reaction solution by centrifugation and subsequent decantation, additionally washed with methanol (2 × 40 mL), and dried overnight in the desiccator under vacuum. All the solution was collected in a round bottom flask and the solvent was removed. The remaining products were dried with rotary evaporation under vacuum.

Analysis of the liquid sample was performed on a Hewlett Packard 6890 series equipped with a HP-5 capillary column and a flame ionization detector (FID). The following operating conditions were used: injection temperature of 300 °C, column temperature program: 40 °C (5 min), 10 °C /min to 280°C (6 min), detection temperature of 300 °C. Quantification of the lignin monomers was performed as follows: Sensitivity factors of the products were obtained by calibration with authentic standards. Identification of lignin monomers was first performed on GC-MS and then confirmed by comparing with authentic standards.

For the reaction described in Supplementary Table 1, Entry 10, the methanol soluble part was purified by column chromatography on silica gel with pentane: ethyl acetate (4:1) as eluent. This afforded dihydroconiferyl alcohol (**1G**) as colorless oil (40 mg).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.73 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 6.59 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 3.57 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.62 - 2.44 (m, 2H), 1.84 - 1.67 (m, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 146.41, 143.66, 133.70, 120.87, 114.26, 111.00, 62.23, 55.83, 34.45, 31.73.

HMRS (ESI) calculated for C₁₀H₁₄O₃ [M+H]⁺: 181.08592, found 181.08698.

4. Synthesis and cleavage of lignin β -O-4 model compounds

S1 (2-(2-Methoxyphenoxy)acetophenone) was synthesized from guaiacol and 2-bromoacetophenone according to a literature procedure⁶². **S1** was obtained as colorless needles with 77% yield after recrystallization from boiling ethanol. ¹H-NMR CDCl₃ (400 MHz): δ 8.01 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.60 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.01-6.87 (m, 2H), 6.85 (d, J = 3.8 Hz, 2H), 5.34 (s, 2H), 3.88 (s, 3H); ¹³C-NMR CDCl₃ (101 MHz): δ 194.6, 149.9, 147.6, 134.7, 133.9, 128.9, 128.2, 122.6, 120.9, 114.9, 112.3, 72.2, 56.0. HMRS (ESI) calculated for C₁₅H₁₅O₃ [M+H]⁺: 243.10157, found 243.10159.

S2 (2-(2-Methoxyphenoxy)-1-phenylethanol) was synthesized from **S1** according to a literature procedure⁶². **S2** was obtained as a white powder in quantitative yield and was used without further purification. ¹H-NMR CDCl₃ (400 MHz): δ 7.44 (d, J = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (t, J = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 7.05 – 6.86 (m, 4H), 5.11 (dd, J = 9.5 Hz, J = 2.7 Hz, 1H), 4.19 (dd, J = 10.1 Hz, J = 2.9 Hz, 1H), 3.98 (t, J = 9.8 Hz, 1H), 2.91 (s, 1H); ¹³C-NMR CDCl₃ (101 MHz): δ 150.0, 148.0, 139.7, 128.5, 128.0, 126.4, 122.5, 121.1, 115.7, 112.0, 76.2, 72.4, 55.9. HMRS (ESI) calculated for C₁₅H₁₆O₃Na ([M+Na]⁺): 267.09917, found 267.09930.7.

The model compound β -Hydroxypropiovanillone (**S3**) was kindly provided by Prof. N. J. Westwood of the University of St. Andrews (UK) and synthesized based on procedure in this literature.⁵⁹

S4 (2-(2-methoxyphenoxy)-1-phenylpropane-1,3-diol) was synthesized according to a literature procedure.⁶³ **S4** was obtained as a mixture of diastereoisomers (1:0.24) in the form of a colorless paste. ¹H-NMR CDCl₃ (400 MHz): δ 7.47-7.26 (m, 6.2H, Ar-H major and minor diastereomer), 7.12-7.04 (m, 1.24H, Ar-H major and minor diastereomer), 7.01-6.88 (m, 3.72H, Ar-H major and minor diastereomer), 5.07-5.03 (m, 1.24H, CH major and minor diastereomer), 4.23-4.15 (m, 1H, CH major diastereomer), 4.09-4.02 (m, 0.24H, CH minor diastereomer), 3.95-3.45 (m, 6.2H, 2xCH and OCH₃ major and minor diastereomer).

S5 (1-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-(2-methoxyphenoxy)propane-1,3-diol) was synthesized according to a literature procedure.⁶³ **S5** was obtained as a mixture of diastereoisomers (1:0.31) in the form of a white paste. ¹H-NMR CDCl₃ (400 MHz): δ 7.10-6.72 (m, 9.17H, Ar-H major and minor diastereomer), 4.95-4.89 (m, 1.31H, CH major and minor diastereomer), 4.13-4.07 (m, 1H, CH major diastereomer), 3.99-3.93 (m, 0.31H, CH minor diastereomer), 3.90-3.36 (m, 14.4H, 2xCH and 3x OCH₃ major and minor diastereomer).

Mechanistic study for the cleavage of lignin β -O-4 model compounds was carried out in a 25 mL high pressure Parr autoclave with an overhead stirrer. Typically, the autoclave was charged with 0.1 g Cu20-PMO catalyst, 0.5 mmol model compound (**S1**, **S2** or **S3**), 20 mg of 3,5-dimethylphenol (internal standard) and 10 mL of methanol. The reactor was sealed and pressured with 40 bar H₂ at room temperature. The reactor was heated to 180 °C for a predetermined amount of time, and stirred at 400 rpm. After the indicated reaction time, the reactor was cooled to room temperature. The products were then analyzed by GC-FID or GC-MS.

5. Extraction and depolymerization of pine organosolv lignin from pine lignocellulose

Extraction of lignin from pine lignocellulose was carried out in a 500 mL autoclave with an overhead stirrer and temperature controller. Typically the reactor was charged with 30 g of pine lignocellulose, 250 mL of methanol at room temperature. The reactor was sealed and stirred for 24 h at 170 °C. During the reaction 25 bar of autogenous pressure developed. After completion of the reaction, the reactor was cooled down to room temperature. The reaction mixture was collected in a 1000 mL beaker by rinsing the reactor several times with methanol and then filtered. The solids were washed with methanol and the combined solution was concentrated to 100 mL by rotary evaporator and precipitated with ice-cold water and then stirred overnight. The mixture was then centrifuged and the hemicellulose containing solutions were decanted. The solids were collected and dried under vacuum yielding 0.66 g organosolv lignin.

Lignin, obtained following the procedure above, was subjected to catalytic depolymerization following the procedure described above in Supplementary Methods Section 3 (0.2 g organosolv lignin as substrate, Cu₂O-PMO 0.2 g, methanol 10 mL, 180 °C, H₂ 40 bar, 18 h, 3,5-dimethylphenol 20 mg as an internal standard).

6. Synthesis of authentic standards

4-ethyl-2,6-dimethoxyphenol (3S): was synthesized according to the reported procedure⁶⁴. 0.5 g 1-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethan-1-one was added in 10 mL iso-propanol, 2.5 g Raney Ni (wet) was added as catalyst. After reflux for 2h at 90 °C, the catalyst was separated and the solvent was evaporated. Colorless oil (0.339 g, 73% yield) was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 70:30). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.38 (s, 2H), 5.52 (*br s*, 1H, OH), 3.81 (s, 6H, OCH₃), 2.53 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.18 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 149.62, 137.96, 135.39, 107.14, 58.82, 31.65, 18.54. HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₀H₁₅O₃ [M+H]⁺: 183.10212; found: 183.10212.

4-allyl-2,6-dimethoxyphenol (50 mg) and 10 mg Pd/C (10 wt.%) were added in 2 mL ethanol to a 5 mL stainless steel high pressure minireactor. Then the reactor was sealed and pressured with 20 bar H₂. After stirring overnight at room temperature the catalyst was separated by filtration and the solvent was evaporated. 2,6-dimethoxy-4-propylphenol (48 mg) was obtained as colorless oil in 95% yield.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.40 (s, 2H), 5.39 (s, 1H), 3.86 (s, 6H), 2.56 - 2.45 (m, 2H), 1.66 - 1.53 (m, 2H), 0.94 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.48, 136.47, 135.30, 107.65, 58.87, 40.92, 27.50, 16.46. HMRS (ESI neg) calculated for C₁₁H₁₇O₃ ([M-H]): 197.11722, found 197.11752.

3,5-Dimethoxy-4-hydroxycinnamaldehyde (0.5 g) and 0.1 g Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ were added in 10 mL methanol to a 100 mL Parr reactor, then the reactor was sealed and pressured to 40 bar with H₂. After stirring overnight at 120 °C the reactor was cooled down and the catalyst was separated by filtration. Methanol was evaporated and 3,5-Dimethoxy-4-hydroxycinnamaldehyde (0.48 g) was obtained as colorless oil (94%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.37 (s, 2H), 3.79 (s, 6H), 3.62 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.57 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 1.86 - 1.76 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 149.66, 135.62, 135.48, 107.73, 64.67, 58.87, 37.05, 34.88. HMRS (ESI neg) calculated for C₁₅H₁₅O₃ ([M-H]): 213.11214, found 213.11243.

7. Determination of lignin content

Lignin content was determined by the acetyl bromide method (ABSL)^{65,66}. The dried lignocellulose chips (between 2 and 5 mg) were added to 10 mL glass vials with 2.5 mL of 25% acetyl bromide in acetic acid. The vials were tightly sealed with Teflon lined caps. Then they were stirred overnight at room temperature until the wall tissue of lignocellulose completely dissolved. The samples were then transferred to 50 mL volumetric flasks containing 2 mL NaOH (2 M). The tubes were rinsed with acetic acid to complete the transfer. Then 0.35 mL of freshly prepared hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 M) was added to the volumetric flasks which were then made up to 50 mL with acetic acid and inverted several times. The absorbance of the solutions was recorded at 280 nm with UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Model DU730, Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA). Lignin content was then calculated based on the calibration curve made with organosolv lignin from Sigma Aldrich. The results are shown in Supplementary Table 5.

8. Mild depolymerization of lignocellulose from different sources

The mild depolymerization of lignocellulose from different sources was based on the same procedure as described in Supplementary Methods Section 3. Typically, the autoclave was charged with 0.2 g Cu20-PMO catalyst, 1 g of lignocellulose, 20 mg of 3,5-dimethylphenol (internal standard) and 10 mL of methanol. The reactor was sealed and pressurized with 40 bar H₂ at room temperature. The reactor was heated to 180 °C for a predetermined amount of time, and stirred at 400 rpm for 18 h. After reaction, the reactor was cooled to room temperature. Then 0.1 mL solution was collected with syringe and injected to GC-MS and GC-FID after filtration with a PTFE filter (0.42 μm). After that all the solution and solids were transferred to a 50 mL centrifuge tube by washing with additional methanol. The solid was separated from the reaction solution by centrifugation and subsequent decantation, and additionally washed with methanol (2 × 40 mL) and dried overnight in the desiccator under vacuum until constant weight. Then the amount of solids was determined by weight. All combined methanol solution was collected in a round bottom flask and the solvent was removed. The weight of the residue (methanol soluble products) was then determined.

9. Treatment of various lignocelluloses without catalyst to obtain organosolv lignin

Lignocelluloses from different origin were treated in methanol in the absence of catalyst based on the same procedure as described in Supplementary Methods Section 3 for control reactions. After reaction the methanol soluble part was concentrated to 10 mL by evaporating part of the solvent and then transferred to a 15 mL centrifuge tube in which methanol was fully removed and the solids were dried in a desiccator until stable weight. Then solids were washed with 10 mL DCM (dichloromethane) and the suspensions were additionally treated in an ultrasonication bath to help solubilization. After centrifugation, the DCM soluble fraction was transferred to a round bottom flask. This process was repeated two times to remove all the DCM soluble products. The DCM was then removed from the combined washings. The DCM soluble products were analyzed by 2D NMR using CDCl₃. The data for the analysis of lignin are shown in Supplementary Tables 4, 5 and Supplementary Figs. 19-25.

10. Conversion of methanol insoluble residues in supercritical methanol

The solid residues obtained after the mild depolymerization reactions (described in Supplementary Methods Section 8) were further treated according to the following procedure: The methanol

insoluble lignocellulose solid residues mixed with the Cu₂O-PMO catalyst were placed in 10 mL Swagelok stainless steel microreactors. Typically, the lignocellulose solids (originating from conversion of 1 g lignocellulose) were first separated to 4 equal parts based on weight and then transferred to 4 identical microreactors. 3 mL methanol was then added to each reactor and they were sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block preheated to 320 °C. After the indicated reaction time, the microreactor was rapidly cooled in an ice-water bath and the content of the reactor was quantitatively transferred to a centrifuge tube. The liquids were separated by centrifugation and decantation and subsequently analyzed by GC-MS-FID. The remaining solids were dried in a desiccator under vacuum for overnight until stable weight.

Qualification of products was performed by GC-MS-FID (Hewlett Packard 5890) equipped with a Restek RTX-1701 capillary column (40 °C maintained for 5 minutes, then increased to 280 °C with a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and maintained for 5 minutes). Percentages of different groups of products were calculated based on the area obtained from the FID detector. Identification of products was performed based on the results from MS detector and major peaks were confirmed by spiking with authentic standards. The results are summarized in Supplementary Figs. 5-12 and Supplementary Table 7.

11. Upgrading alcohol mixtures SMix1 to alkanes with cyclopentanone

Coupling reactions of 1-pentanol with cyclopentanone

Coupling reactions of 1-pentanol with cyclopentanone were performed in a 10 mL Swagelok stainless steel microreactor. In a typical experiment, 1-pentanol and cyclopentanone were placed in the microreactor and heptane was added as solvent. Then specified amount of catalyst was added, the reactor was sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at the desired temperature. After the indicated reaction time, the microreactor was cooled down in an ice-water bath and the liquid sample was separated by filtration. The collected samples were then analyzed by GC-FID and GC-MS.

Experimental procedure for solvent exchange and coupling

The methanol solution **SMix1**, (generated from the catalytic processing of the lignocellulose residues in supercritical methanol, using 1 g pine lignocellulose as substrate) was separated from the catalyst by filtration, and was transferred to a 50 mL round bottom flask to which 10 mL heptane was added. Methanol was then removed by distillation in a special distillation apparatus equipped with an oil/water separator filter funnel, at 105 °C. After distillation, a light yellow heptane solution containing most of the alcohol products was obtained. As can be seen from the GC-FID traces below, most of the aliphatic alcohols were successfully transferred into heptane, while there was also a small amount of heptane insolubles (~30 mg of brown oily material). The heptane solution (8 mL) was divided to two 4 mL portions and these were transferred to two identical 10 mL Swagelok stainless steel microreactors. Then cyclopentanone and CuNi-PMO catalyst were added. The reactors were sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at the desired temperature. After the indicated reaction time, the microreactors were cooled down in an ice-water bath and the liquid sample was separated by filtration with a PTFE filter (0.42 μm). The collected samples were then analyzed by GC-MS. To better understand the composition of the heptane insoluble oil, the sample was dissolved in 2ml DCM, since it is good polar solvent and cannot originate from the sample and the sample was analyzed by GC-MS.

Hydrodeoxygenation of the ketones obtained from the coupling of SMix1 with cyclopentanone to alkanes

Hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) reactions were carried out in a 100 mL high pressure Parr autoclave. In a typical experiment, the heptane solution containing 4-propylcyclohexanone or all the ketones after the coupling reaction (as described in Supplementary Note 7) was made up to 10 mL with additional heptane, and then transferred to the reactor. Ni/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ was added as catalyst and then the reactor was sealed and pressurized with 40 bar H₂. The reactor was heated to 250 °C and the stirring was kept at 400 rpm for 6h. After reaction the reactor was cooled to room temperature or 0 °C with ice water and the solution was analyzed in detail by GC-MS and GC-FID as described in Supplementary Note 8. The heptane insoluble part was dissolved in 0.4ml methanol while treated in an ultrasonication bath to help solubilization, then transferred to a 100 ml Parr reactor and 10ml heptane was added, the hydrodeoxygenation reaction was then carried out based on the same conditions above.

The recycling was performed as follows: After reaction the content of the reactor was transferred to a centrifuge tube with additional 4 mL heptane and centrifuged. The heptane solution was separated from the catalyst by subsequent decantation. Fresh, 4 mL of heptane was added to the catalyst, ultrasonicated and centrifuged again. The heptane washings were combined and an additional 20 mg of eicosane was added as an internal standard. The leftover catalyst in the centrifuge tube and the glass insert were dried in a desiccator overnight at room temperature in vacuum. For the next run, the catalyst was transferred to the glass insert, its weight was determined, then 0.23 mL (1.5 mmol) of substrate and 10 mL of heptane were added and the filled glass insert was transferred to a 100 mL Parr® reactor and the catalytic procedure was performed. The whole procedure was repeated for 11 runs. Since the substrate was fully converted to propyl cyclohexane with 99% selectivity, double amount of substrate was used for 12th to 14th cycle and the substrate amount was gradually increased as indicated on Supplementary Fig. 87.

In order to minimize the loss of catalyst, the same centrifuge tube was used for the catalyst separation. After 20th cycles, only 81 mg catalyst was recovered and this means in average 6 mg catalyst was lost for each cycle during the recycling test.

For the recycling test, 4-propylcyclohexanone was selected as model compound. The catalyst showed extremely high robustness.

12. Experimental procedures for synthesis of compounds

Compound 3G

20 mg compound **1G** was added in a 10 mL Swagelok stainless steel microreactor with 10 mg Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ as catalyst, then 3 mL toluene was added as solvent. The reactor was sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at the 220 °C for 18 h. Then the reactor was cooled in ice-water. The catalyst was separated by filtration and the solution was analyzed by GC-MS and GC-FID. Herein, 4 reactions were set up at the same time. After reaction, the reaction mixtures were combined and then toluene was evaporated. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using hexanes: ethyl acetate (1:1) as eluent. Yield: 51 mg, (75%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.86 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.72 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 2.61 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.24 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 149.02, 146.18, 138.93, 122.93, 116.86, 113.19, 58.50, 31.22, 18.60.

HMRS (ESI⁺) calculated for C₉H₁₁O₂ [M+H]⁺: 151.07536, found 151.07643.

Compound 4

20mg **1G** was added in a 10 mL Swagelok stainless steel microreactor with 20mg Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ as catalyst, and then 3 mL ammonia solution in THF (0.4 M) was added as a solvent. The reactor was sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at the 180 °C for 24h. Four reactions using 4 identical microreactors were used at the same time. After reaction the reactor was cooled in ice-water. The catalyst was separated by filtration and the solution was analyzed by GC-MS and GC-FID. For purification, we combined all 4 reaction mixtures and the solvent was removed. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, hexanes: ethyl acetate (2:1). Yield: 54 mg (69%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.87 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.74 – 6.71 (m, 2H), 5.59 (s, 1H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 2.88 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 2.59 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 149.29, 147.46, 132.64, 123.61, 121.91, 117.32, 113.54, 58.60, 33.99, 22.43.

HMRS (ESI⁺) calculated for C₁₀H₁₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 176.07061, found 176.07161.

Compound 5

Compound **4** (44 mg, 0.25 mmol) was placed in a 4 mL glass vial with a magnetic stirring bar and dissolved in MeOH (1.7 mL). The Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst was added and the vial was quickly transferred to a 5 mL stainless steel reactor, which was pressurized with H₂ (20 bar). The reactor was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (110 °C) and the reaction was left under magnetic stirring for 5 hours. After this time, the reactor was cooled to room temperature and vented. The mixture was filtered on a PTFE filter (0.25 μm pore size) and the volatiles were evaporated under reduced pressure to give an analytically pure sample of **5**. Alternatively, the hydrochloride salt can be isolated as yellow solid (95%, 43 mg) by adding HCl solution in MeOH to a solution of amine **5** in diethyl ether (10 mL).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 6.74 (dd, *J* = 5.3, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 6.68 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.65-2.61 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.56-2.51 (m, 2H), 1.74 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 150.19, 147.03, 135.93, 122.98, 117.42, 114.33, 57.58, 43.29, 36.92, 35.03.

HRMS (ESI⁻) calculated for C₁₀H₁₄NO₂ [M-H]⁻: 180.1025; found: 180.1030.

Compound 6

100 mg (0.56 mmol) compound **4** was added to a 20 mL microwave vial, then 10 mL 1 M NaOH was added. The reactor was sealed and placed in a pre-heated aluminum block at the 100 °C for 24 h. After cooling to room temperature, the mixture was extracted with Et₂O (20 mL), and the aqueous phase was acidified with conc. HCl (pH = 2), extracted with Et₂O (3 × 20 mL) and the combined organic layers were washed with brine (20 mL), dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure by rotary evaporation. Purification was carried out by flash column chromatography on silica gel, using ethyl acetate: methanol (20:1) as eluent. Yield: 80 mg (72%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.84 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 6.71-6.69 (m, 2H), 5.51 (b, 1H, OH), 3.87 (s, 3H), 2.89 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 2.65 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 181.00, 149.08, 146.75, 134.72, 123.49, 117.04, 113.56, 58.52, 38.52, 33.00.

HMRS (ESI⁺) calculated for C₁₀H₁₁O₄ [M+H]⁺: 195.06519, found 195.06658.

Compound 6Cy

Preparation of 3,4-dimethoxyphenylpropanoic acid.

392 mg (2 mmol) dihydroferuleic acid was measured out to a Stainless steel microreactor then 5 mL dimethylcarbonate (DMC) and 69 mg (0.5 mmol) K₂CO₃ were added. The microreactor was closed and heated to 210 °C for 12 h. After cooling down to room temperature the product mixture was extracted by MeOH then concentrated in vacuum to yield 555 mg solid residue. The residue was transferred to a round bottom flask and 336 mg (6 mmol) of KOH was added with 0.6 mL of water and 0.6 mL of Et₂O. It was stirred vigorously for 40 hours at RT after which the organic phase was separated. Then 1 mL HCl was added to the aqueous phase and it was extracted by EtOAc for 3 times. The organic phases were combined, dried over Na₂SO₄ then concentrated in vacuum to yield 332 mg (75%) of 3,4-dimethoxyphenylpropanoic acid.

Preparation of 6Cy from 3,4-dimethoxyphenylpropanoic acid.

315 mg (1.5 mmol) 3,4-dimethoxyphenylpropanoic acid was measured out to a 500 mL round bottom flask equipped with a PTFE coated mechanical stirrer, then 7.8 g polyphosphoric acid (PPA) was added. The flask was heated to 100 °C for 2 hours under stirring, during the reaction the colour of the viscous mixture turned to caramel brown. After reaction, the solution was quenched with 30 g crushed ice, which was added to the mixture by funnel next to the stirrer, and then 12.5 g (90.6 mmol) K₂CO₃ was added slowly and stirred until the ice melted. The solution was concentrated in vacuum then extracted 5 times with EtOAc (15 mL). The organic phase was dried on Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated in vacuum to yield 152 mg pure crystals. The glue like salt (K₂HPO₄) was further treated with 4.984 g (89 mmol) KOH in 30 mL water. The aqueous phase was then extracted 3 times by Et₂O. The organic phases were combined, dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated in vacuum to yield additional 53 mg pure 5,6-dimethoxy-1-indanone. Overall yield: 205 mg (53%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.18 (s, 1H), 6.89 (s, 1H), 3.96 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.90 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.05 (m, 2H), 2.67 (m, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): 208.35, 158.04, 153.04, 152.03, 132.55, 110.13, 106.83, 58.86, 39.17, 28.23.

HRMS (APCI+, m/z): calculated for C₁₁H₁₃O₃ [M+H]⁺: 193.08646; found: 193.08599.

Compound 7

Compound **7** was obtained by following a palladium-catalyzed decarboxylative reaction developed by Gooßen et al.⁶⁷

The carboxylic acid **6** (105 mg, 0.5 mmol), PdCl₂ (8.85 mg, 0.05 mmol, 10 mol%) and DPEphos (80.8 mg, 0.15 mmol, 30 mol%) were placed in a 5 mL screw-cap glass tube, which was evacuated and refilled with argon 3 times. NMP (2 mL) and Piv₂O (2 equiv., 0.2 mL) were sequentially added and the suspension was evacuated one more time and refilled with argon in order to degas the added liquids. The glass tube was heated at 110 °C in a metal heating block for 14 hours. After cooling down, the mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (20 mL) and filtered over silica gel and a sample was analyzed by GC-MS, which showed 84% selectivity to the product (with the pivalic ester of the styrene product being the a by-product). The organic phase was extracted with HCl (aq), water and brine, dried over MgSO₄ and filtered. After evaporation of the solvent, the crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (5:1) as eluent. Yield: 54 mg (72%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.95-6.87 (m, 3H), 6.64 (dd, *J* = 17.5, 10.9 Hz, 1H), 5.68 (b, 1H, OH), 5.60 (d, *J* = 17.5 Hz, 1H), 5.13 (d, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H), 3.91 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 146.55, 145.57, 136.59, 130.23, 120.04, 114.32, 111.46, 107.94, 55.86.

HRMS (ESI⁻) calculated for C₉H₉O₂ [M-H]⁻: 149.0603; found: 149.0610.

Compound 7S

A dry and degassed Schlenk tube was loaded under argon with 92 mg of 2-methoxy-4-vinylphenol (0.61 mmol), 7.6 mg of Hoveyda catalyst (0.012 mmol, 2 mol%) and 2 mL of DMC. The reaction was stirred at 80 °C for 3 h. After solvent evaporation, the product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using ethyl acetate: pentane (1:1) as eluent. Yield: 0.100 g (60%).

The NMR data were consistent with the reported data⁶⁸.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 7.10 (d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 2H, H-2, 2'), 6.95 (dd, *J* = 8.0 Hz, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 2H, H-6, 6'), 6.91 (s, 2H, H-7, 7'), 6.75 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H, H-5, 5'), 3.90 (s, 6H, 3, 3'- OCH₃).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD): δ 150.40 (C-3, 3', C-4, 4'), 132.79 (C-1, 1'), 128.49 (C-7, 7'), 122.03 (C-6, 6'), 117.54 (C-5, 5'), 111.49 (C-2, 2'), 57.62 (3, 3'- OCH_3).

HRMS (APCI $^+$, m/z) calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 273.11267; found: 273.11214.

Compound 8

To a solution of 4-ethylguaiacol (10 mmol, 1.52 g) in acetonitrile (30 mL) were subsequently added potassium carbonate (11 mmol, 1.52 g) and diethylcarbamoyl chloride (11 mmol, 1.49 g). The mixture was heated under reflux for 14 hours, then cooled down to room temperature. The solid was filtered and the solvent was removed by evaporation, the oily residue was dissolved in diethyl ether and washed with a 20 wt% solution of KOH. The organic phase was dried over magnesium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated. A pure product could be obtained after column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (5:1) as eluent. Yield: 2.10 g (84%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 6.98 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.78-6.72 (m, 2H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.50-3.31 (m, 4H), 2.62 (q, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 1.32-1.12 (overlapping signals, m, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.00, 154.03, 145.01, 141.18, 125.57, 122.42, 114.83, 58.52, 31.48, 18.32.

HRMS (ESI $^+$) Calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 252.1600; found: 252.1592.

Compounds 9a-9e

Compound 9 was obtained by following the procedure developed by Mamoru Tobisu and Naoto Chatani.⁶⁹

In a nitrogen-filled glovebox, $\text{Ni}(\text{COD})_2$ (0.04 mmol, 10 mg), $i\text{PrNHC}$ (0.08 mmol, 32 mg) and NaO^tBu (0.5 mmol, 48 mg) were placed in a schlenk tube equipped with a magnetic bar. The schlenk was taken out of the glovebox and the nitrogen atmosphere was replaced with argon. Degassed toluene (2 mL) was added to the solids and the suspension was stirred for 5 minutes while the color turned from yellow to red-brown, then the substrate (0.25 mmol) and the N-nucleophile (0.35 mmol) were sequentially added. The mixture was stirred at 120 °C for 21 hours; the suspension was filtered over

silica using ethyl acetate as eluent and analyzed by GC-MS. The pure product was obtained by column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (9:1) as eluent.

9a Yield: 0.035 g (64%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.86 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.76 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.72-6.70 (m, 1H), 3.90-3.86 (m, 7H), 3.04 (m, 4H), 2.61 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.23 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 154.80, 142.06, 141.51, 122.53, 120.50, 113.87, 69.89, 57.98, 54.00, 31.17, 18.24.

HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₂₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 222.14939; found: 222.14890.

9b Yield: 0.043 g (75%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.30-7.25 (m, 3H), 7.13 (m, 2H), 6.92 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 6.77-6.74 (m, 2H), 6.04 (b, NH, 1H), 3.90 (s, 3H), 2.64 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.27 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 151.37, 146.08, 139.36, 132.98, 131.88, 123.17, 122.32, 120.40, 118.39, 113.17, 58.25, 31.31, 18.53.

HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₅H₁₈NO [M+H]⁺: 228.13883; found: 228.13829.

9c Yield: 0.052 g (81%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.11 (dd, *J* = 8.8 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 2H), 7.01 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.87 (dd, *J* = 8.8 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 2H), 6.71 (d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 6.69 (dd, *J* = 8.0 Hz, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 5.86 (b, NH, 1H), 3.90 (s, 3H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.61 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.25 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 157.54, 150.35, 138.81, 137.87, 135.13, 124.55, 122.37, 117.24, 116.00, 112.90, 58.24, 58.21, 31.22, 18.60.

HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₆H₂₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 258.14939; found: 258.14886.

Yield: 0.036 g (59%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.00 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.92 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.71-6.64 (m, 4H), 5.78 (b, NH, 1H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 3.49 (b, NH, 2H), 2.59 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.23 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 150.04, 144.24, 137.25, 136.96, 135.89, 125.65, 122.37, 118.81, 115.43, 112.78, 58.20, 31.18, 18.61.

HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₅H₂₀N₂O [M+H]⁺: 243.14973; found: 243.14930.

Yield: 0.032 g (48%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.17-7.13 (m, 3H), 6.73 (s, 1H), 6.56 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.07 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 5.58 (b, NH, 1H), 3.96 (s, 3H), 2.60 (m, 4H), 2.21 (s, 3H), 1.23 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H), 1.17 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 149.33, 144.53, 140.86, 138.97, 136.86, 135.99, 131.05, 129.17, 128.41, 122.45, 113.75, 112.51, 58.32, 31.07, 27.31, 21.01, 18.45, 17.52.

HRMS (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₈H₂₄NO [M+H]⁺: 270.18577; found: 270.18543.

Regarding the pathways from **1G** to **3G** and the follow up steps from **3G**, these were initially performed with commercially available **1G** and **3G**. Subsequently it was shown that the whole sequence till **9c** (**1G**⇒**3G**⇒**8**⇒**9c**) can be integrated starting from **1G** isolated from lignocellulose and following the same procedure with very negligible variation of product yields.

Compound 10

Compound **9** was obtained by following the procedure developed by Paula Alvarez-Bercedo and Ruben Martin.⁷⁰

In a nitrogen-filled glovebox, a mixture of $[\text{Ni}(\text{COD})_2]$ (0.02 mmol) and PCy_3 (0.04 mmol) was placed in a 5 mL screw-cap tube and dissolved in toluene (1 mL). The substrate **8** (0.2 mmol) and TMSO (0.3 mmol) were subsequently added and the mixture was stirred at 110 °C for 14h. The volatiles were removed under vacuum and the residue was filtered over celite and analyzed by GC-MS. The pure product was isolated by column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (95:5) as eluent. Yield: 0.026 g (94%).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.23 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 1H), 6.83 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H), 6.80-6.73 (m, 2H), 3.83 (s, 3H), 2.66 (q, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 1.27 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 159.65, 145.92, 129.26, 120.29, 113.67, 110.83, 55.10, 28.94, 15.53.

HRMS (ESI⁺) calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{O}$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 137.0966; found: 137.0958.

Compound 11

This procedure was adapted from the work of Guy L. Plourde.⁷¹

To a pre-cooled solution (0 °C) of **1G** (1 mmol, 182 mg) in MeOH (1.5 mL) was added dropwise a solution of iodobenzene diacetate (PIDA) (1.05 equiv., 338 mg) in the same solvent (1 mL). The color immediately turned into bright yellow and the homogeneous solution was stirred for 15 min at room temperature. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using hexane: ethyl acetate (2:1) as eluent. Yield: 0.133 g (78%).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 6.81 (dd, $J = 9.6$ Hz, 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.14 (d, $J = 9.6$ Hz, 1H), 5.71 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 4.13-4.03 (m, 2H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 2.21-2.15 (m, 2H), 2.12-2.06 (m, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 179.79, 175.58, 150.80, 146.17, 128.07, 113.08, 81.00, 55.24, 33.12, 28.27.

HRMS (ESI⁻) calculated for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$: 181.08592; found: 181.08580.

Compound **12a**

Compound **11** (0.1 mmol, 18 mg) was dissolved in a 9:1 mixture of MeOH-H₂O (1 mL) and glycine methyl ester hydrochloride (0.7 mmol, 88 mg) and triethylamine (0.9 mmol, 0.125 mL) were subsequently added. The mixture was stirred at 40 °C for 3 hours and the volatiles were removed. The pure compound was obtained by column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (9:1) as eluent. Yield: 0.017 g (95%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz): δ 6.66-6.60 (m, 3H), 3.83 (s, 3H), 3.66 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 2H), 2.61 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 1.89-1.82 (m, 2H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 147.40, 133.89, 132.22, 120.58, 115.08, 110.79, 62.39, 55.44, 34.56, 31.75.

HRMS (ESI⁻) calculated for C₁₀H₁₄NO₂ [M-H]⁻: 180.1025; found: 180.1031.

Compound **12b**

This procedure was adapted from the work of Alaniz and coworkers⁷².

Iodobenzene diacetate (PIDA) (0.354 g, 1.1 mmol) or phenyliodine bis(trifluoroacetate) (PIFA) (0.473 g, 1.1 mmol) was suspended in MeOH (5 mL) and cooled on an ice bath. The phenol (1.0 mmol, 0.182 g) was dissolved in MeOH (5 mL) and added dropwise over 5 min. The ice bath was removed and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min or until consumption of the starting material. The reagents Et₃N (1.3 mL, 9 mmol, 9 equiv), H₂O (0.5 mL), and methyl glycinate hydrochloride (0.883 g, 7 mmol, 7 equiv) were added sequentially and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C for overnight or until consumption of the quinone. The solvent was evaporated; DCM (50 mL) was added and extracted with HCl (aq) (1 M, 6 x 10 mL). The aqueous layers were combined, neutralized with saturated NaHCO₃ (aq) (140 mL), and extracted with DCM (3 x 50 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The product was isolated after chromatography column on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (5:1) as eluent. Yield: 125 mg (83%).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.67-6.62 (m, 3H), 3.85 (s, 3H), 2.56 (q, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.21 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 150.04, 137.58, 136.25, 122.57, 117.71, 113.00, 58.10, 31.12, 18.65.
HRMS (ESI $^-$) calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$ $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$: 152.10699; found: 152.10704.

When the reaction was performed using **1G** isolated from lignocellulose reaction (Supplementary Table 1, Entry 10), following the same procedure slightly lower isolated yield (61%) was obtained.

Compound 12c

This compound was obtained according to general procedure for the *one-pot conversion of quaiacol derivatives to anilines* (compound **3G** to **12b**).⁷²

PIDA (0.354 g, 1.1 mmol) was suspended in MeOH (5 mL) and cooled on an ice bath. The phenol (1.0 mmol, 0.259 g) was dissolved in MeOH (5 mL) and added dropwise over 5 min. The ice bath was removed and then the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min or until consumption of the starting material. The reagents Et_3N (1.3 mL, 9 mmol, 9 equiv), H_2O (0.5 mL), and methyl glycinate hydrochloride (0.883 g, 7 mmol, 7 equiv) were added sequentially and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C overnight or until consumption of the quinone. The solvent was evaporated; DCM (50 mL) was added and the organic layer was extracted with HCl (aq) (1 M, 6 x 10 mL). The aqueous layers were combined, neutralized with saturated NaHCO_3 (aq) (140 mL), and extracted with DCM (3 x 50 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The product was isolated after chromatography column on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (4:1) as eluent. Yield: 198 mg (77%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 6.65-6.57 (m, 3H), 4.37 (b, NH, 1H), 3.84 (s, 3H), 3.16-3.11 (m, 2H), 2.93 (s, 3H), 2.60 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.86 (q, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 150.11, 136.86, 133.68, 123.22, 117.74, 113.41, 58.14, 45.34, 42.89, 35.01, 34.54.

HRMS (ESI $^+$) calculated for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 259.1116; found: 259.1110.

Compound 13

Compound **13** was obtained by modification of a reported procedure.⁷³

A Schlenk tube was charged with compound **1G** (90 mg, 0.5 mmol), MsNH_2 (43 mg, 0.45 mmol), $[\text{Ru}(\text{p-cymene})\text{Cl}]_2$ (0.0125 mmol, 8 mg), DPEphos (0.025 mmol, 13 mg) and K_2CO_3 (0.05 mmol, 7 mg). After evacuating and filling the Schlenk with argon (3 times), degassed toluene (1 mL) was added under argon flow and the reaction mixture was heated at 130 °C for 24 hours. After cooling down to room temperature, the solution was filtered through celite and the toluene was evaporated. Pure **13** was obtained by column chromatography on silica gel, using pentane: ethyl acetate (9:1) as eluent. Yield: 60 mg (52%).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 6.82 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.69-6.64 (m, 2H), 5.56 (s, OH, 1H), 4.54 (s, NH, 1H), 3.87 (s, 3H), 3.15-3.09 (m, 2H), 2.93 (s, 3H), 2.62 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 1.86 (q, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 149.18, 146.59, 135.33, 123.53, 117.01, 113.71, 58.59, 45.26, 42.84, 34.98, 34.54.

HRMS (ESI $^-$) calculated for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$ [M-H] $^-$: 258.0800; found: 258.0807.

Compound **14**

Compounds **14** were obtained by modification of a reported procedure.⁷⁴

A mixture of the (hydroxyalkyl)phenol (0.182 g, 1 mmol) and vinyl acetate (0.140 mL, 1.5 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) in 7 mL acetonitrile was heated in the presence of CsF (0.1 mmol, 0.1 equiv.) at 70 °C for 3 hours. The solid was filtered off and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residual oil was purified by column chromatography to give the pure product as colorless oil in 75% yield (0.168 g).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 6.93 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.80 – 6.76 (m, 2H), 3.82 (s, 3H), 3.69 (td, $J = 6.4$, 1.3 Hz, 2H), 2.69 (dd, $J = 8.7$, 6.8 Hz, 2H), 2.30 (s, 3H), 1.92 – 1.85 (m, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 169.48, 150.71, 140.98, 137.64, 122.40, 120.44, 112.59, 61.87, 55.76, 34.10, 32.00, 20.68.

HRMS (ESI $^-$) calculated for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{33}\text{O}_7$ [M-H] $^-$: 225.11214; found: 225.11212.

Compound **15**

Compound **15** was synthesized according to a reported procedure.⁷⁵

To a solution of compound **14** (1 mmol) in dry CH₃CN, (1 mL) in a 10 mL glass test tube were added the following solutions: [Cu(MeCN)₄]BF₄ (0.05 mmol in 1 mL CH₃CN), 2,2'-dipyridyl (0.05 mmol in 1 mL CH₃CN), TEMPO (0.05 mmol in 1 mL CH₃CN) and N-methyl imidazole (0.1 mmol in 1 mL CH₃CN). The dark red mixture was stirred overnight under atmospheric oxygen (a balloon was used) while the color changed from red-brown to green. The mixture was diluted with water (20 mL) and extracted three times with ethyl acetate (3x20 mL), the combined organic phase was dried over MgSO₄ and filtered. After the evaporation of the solvent, the pure compound was obtained after flash chromatography (silica gel, pentane/ethyl acetate) in quantitative yield.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 9.79 (t, J = 1.3 Hz, 1H), 6.92 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.78 – 6.73 (m, 2H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 2.91 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 2.77 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 2.28 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 201.32, 169.17, 150.91, 139.39, 138.06, 122.69, 120.29, 112.58, 55.79, 45.22, 27.92, 20.64.

HRMS (ESI⁻) calculated for C₁₂H₁₃O₄ [M-H]⁻: 221.0814; found: 221.0819.

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